

"Impact of RBSK and District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC) for identification and treatment of 4Ds (Defects at Birth, Diseases, Deficiency, Developmental Delays including Disabilities) among 0 to 18 year children in Koraput Dist.of Odisha".

Dissertation Submitted to

The IIHMR University, Jaipur

for the partial fulfilment for the award of the degree of

Executive Masters in Public Health Management

Odisha

by

Bibhu Ranjan Mund

Roll No- IHMR-U/12/2021-23/0015

Under the Supervision and Guidance of

Dr Goutam Sadhu

2021-23

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation titled “**Impact of RBSK & District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC) for identification and treatment of 4Ds (Defects at Birth, Diseases, Deficiency, Developmental Delays including Disabilities) among 0 to 18 year children in Koraput Dist. of Odisha**” is the bonafide record of my original research work. I declare that it has not been submitted to any other university or institution for the award of any degree or diploma. Information derived from the published or unpublished work of others has been duly acknowledged in the text.

Signature-

Name- Bibhu Ranjan Mund

Roll No- IHMR-U/12/2021-23/0015

Date-

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that dissertation titled “Impact of RBSK & District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC) for identification and treatment of 4Ds (Defects at Birth, Diseases, Deficiency, Developmental Delays including Disabilities) among 0 to 18 year children in Koraput Dist. of Odisha” is a record of the research work undertaken by Sri Bibhu Ranjan Mund in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Executive Masters in Public Health Management from the IIHMR University, Jaipur under my guidance and supervision and his/her approach to the research study has been sincere, scientific, and analytical. I hereby declare that this dissertation titled is the bonafide record of my original research work. I declare that it has not been submitted to any other university or institution for the award of any degree or diploma. Information derived from the published or unpublished work of others has been duly acknowledged in the text.

Faculty Guide

IIHMR University, Jaipur

Date-

School Dean

IIHMR University, Jaipur

Date-

List of Abbreviations

ASHA	Accredited Social Health Activist
AYUSH	Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy
BCC	Behavioural Change Communication
CHC	Community Health Centre
DEIC	District Early Intervention Centre
GOI	Government of India
ICDS	Integrated Child Development Services
ICTC	Integrated Counselling and Testing Centre
IEC	Information, Education and Communication
IPHS	Indian Public Health Standards
IT	Information Technology
MO	Medical Officer
MPHW	Multi Purpose Health Worker
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
NHM	National Health Mission
NRHM	National Rural Health Mission
NUHM	National Urban Health Mission
OOPE	Out of Pocket Expenditure
OPD	Out-Patient Department
PHC	Primary Health Centre
RBSK	RashtriyaBalSwasthyaKaryakram
RCH	Reproductive and Child Health
S&ME	School & Mass Education Department
SSD	ST&SC Development Department
TOR	Terms of Reference
UHC	Universal Health Coverage
VHND	Village Health and Nutrition Day
W&CD	Women & Child Welfare Department

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- Health is one of the important aspects of life, which not only determines physical condition of a person but also influences socio-economic-educational status of the family.

India has the largest number of children between the ages of 0-18 years in the globe which is approximately 37% of the entire population. India contributes 20% to global child death. The Govt. of India has introduced several initiatives and programmes over the years to address the country's poor child health and survival status and Rashtriya Bal Swasthya Karyamram (RBSK) is one of them which is launched in 2013 aiming at child health screening, early identification and early intervention for children from birth to 18 years to cover 4D's viz. defects at birth, deficiencies, Diseases and developmental delays including disabilities. The programme aims to cover over 1.21 crores children from birth till 18 years under its domain. Screening of the new-born, both at home & public-health facilities, Pre-schooling children up to 6 years from Anganwari centres & school going children & adolescents from age 6-18 years studying in Government & Government aided schools are the targeted beneficiaries under this programme. The prevalence rate in India for 4D as follows:

4D	Name of the Health Condition	Prevalence (Followed from RBSK Resource material)
Birth defect	Neural tube Condition	4.1 per 1000 live births
	Down's Syndrome	1.09 per 1000 live births
	Cleft Lip & Palate	0.93 for every 1000 live births
	Club Foot	1-2 per 1000 live birth
	Developmental dysplasia of the hip	1 in 1000 children born
	Congenital cataract	1-1.5/10,000 children
	Congenital deafness	5.6 to 10 / 1000 live births
	Congenital heart diseases	8-10 /1000 live births
	Retinopathy of Prematurity	20-22% of premature children*
Childhood deficiencies	Severe Anaemia	3% children are severely anaemic as per NFHS-3
	Vitamin A deficiency (Bitot spot)	0.6-0.7% in children
	Vitamin D Deficiency, (Rickets)	12.5% suffer with Vit-D deficiency
	SAM	6%
	Otitis Media	8.60%
	Rheumatic heart disease	1.5 / 1000- in school children in the age group 5 to 9 years and 0.13 to 1.1 per 1000 in the age group of 10 to 14 years
	Reactive airway disease	5% in children aged 1 month to 14 years
	Dental conditions	50-60 % among preschool
	Convulsive disorders	0.8 % to 0.35%
Developmental delays and disabilities	Vision Impairment	3% of children 6-14 yrs
	Hearing Impairment	5.4% in Children < 10 years
	Neuro motor Impairment	2%
	Cognitive delay	4.79%
	Language delay	6%
	Behaviour disorder (Autism)	0.50%
	Learning disorder	8%
Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder	7%	

Further 20% (approx) of the babies discharged from the SNCUs are suffering from Developmental delays or disabilities at a later stage. These delays if not intervened timely may lead to permanent disabilities with regard to cognition, hearing and vision etc. for which they will be directly affect the GDP of the Country lateron.

Methodology- The study was done in Koraput District of Odisha. The study is descriptive in nature and the data has been collected from the District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC) & Mobile Health Teams-RBSK through personal interaction and Client Satisfaction through Google Form in online mode using pre- structured questionnaire.

Results- Gradually maximum health indicators & practices under the age group of 0-18 are improving due to early intervention of RBSK in Koraput district. Newborn screening at Delivery Points is gradually improving from 06% in 2014-15 upto 100% in 2022-23. The result of the analysis clearly demonstrated that clients are much satisfied with the 4D services provided by the DEIC & RBSK which is reaching upto the mark.

Conclusion- Capacity building of all DEIC Staff including Exposure visits to different States may be provided so that it will be a conducive environment for implementation of all activities under DEIC & RBSK. Also more infrastructures including Equipment/instrument for screening of Newborns/children may be provided to DEIC for strengthening. Management of Birth Defects at District level hospitals should be strengthened.

RBSK Programme is always providing a qualitative & effective platform for early screening of 0-18 year children including early identification of 4D through Mobile Health Teams-RBSK for which it is now easy to manage/treat them at primary/secondary/tertiary level instritutions.

Gaps in providing infrastructure and strengthening the secondary services at district level including equipping the health systems so that identified 4D cases can be managed easily minimizing the newborn/child death i.e. reducing the IMR/U5MR.

(4D children with their attendants, DEIC Staff at DEIC, RBSK Koraput)

Introduction:

This chapter represents the reason why I am interested in study of the effectiveness of RBSK & DEIC activities in Koraput district of Odisha.

1.1. Background Information :

1.1.1 – Introduction to RBSK & DEIC:-

RBSK Programme is focusing on 42 identified health conditions under '4D' approach to be addressed through Child Health Screening and Early Intervention services. The dedicated Mobile Medical Teams have been engaged at each Block to cover at least once in a year to non-Residential Schools, bi-annually to Anganwari centres and quarterly to the Residential Schools. The children needing special care has been focussed through District Early Intervention Centres (DEIC) & empanelled Hospital for required & specific case.

1.1.2 - 4Ds' under RBSK :

	Defects at Birth: Total
1	Neural tube defect
2	Down's Syndrome
3	Cleft Lip & Palate
4	Club foot
5	Developmental dysplasia of the
6	Congenital cataract
7	Congenital deafness
8	Congenital heart diseases
9	Retinopathy of Prematurity
10	Microcephaly
11	Macrocephaly
Deficiencies: Total	
12	Severe Anaemia
13	Vitamin A deficiency (Bitot spot)
14	Vitamin D Deficiency, (Rickets)
15	A) SAM
	B) Severe Thinning
	C) Obesity
16	Goitre
17	Severe Stunting
18	Vitamin B complex deficiency.
Childhood Diseases: Total	
19	Skin conditions
20	Otitis Media
21	Rheumatic heart disease
22	Reactive airway disease
23	Dental Conditions
24	Convulsive disorders
25	Childhood leprosy Disease
26	Childhood T.B.
27	Childhood Extra Pulmonary T.

	Developmental Delays including Disabilities
28	Vision impairment
29	Hearing Impairment
30	Neuro motor impairment
31	Motor delay
32	Cognitive delay
33	Language delay
34	Behaviour disorder (Autism)
35	Learning disorder
36	Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
	Others
Adolescent Health: Total	
37	Growing up concerns
38	Substance abuse
39	Feel depressed
40	Delay in menstruation cycles
41	Irregular periods
42	Pain or burning sensation while urinating
43	Discharge/ foul smelling discharge urinary area
44	Pain during menstruation
45	

Screening Platforms:

To cover all the children within the age group of 0 to 18 years and for systematic screening following screening platforms are being used under this programme:

- Comprehensive New-born Screening (both Community and facility level)

- Routine Health Screening at AWCs & Schools by dedicated Mobile Health Team (MHT)s
- Assessment at District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC)

Package of Services

The services can be categorised into following groups:

Community Services:

- **New-born Screening at community level:** Screening of home delivery children are screened through ASHA for identification of visible Birth Defects. The suspected/identified children are intimated to concern MHTs through ANMs for early referral.

- **Routine Health Screening by Mobile Health Team (MHT)s**

Mobile Health Team (MHT)s are engaged at Block level @ 2 teams per Block to visit regularly to AWC & Schools for screening of all pre-school & school going children under the programme. In Odisha 636 MHTs are functional for the purpose.

- **Composition:** Each Team comprising of 4 staff i.e., one AYUSH Doctor (Male), One AYUSH Doctor (Female), One Pharmacist and one ANM/Staff Nurse.
- **Mobility of Team:** The teams are provided with dedicated vehicle for mobility of staff to the screening site and carrying screening equipment.
- **Screening Equipment:** The teams are being provided with Anthropometric Instruments & Development Assessment kit. Around 30 types of screening kits are provided to each team for screening of children.
- **Screening Modalities:** The team thoroughly screen the children from 'Head to toes' to identify the undiagnosed health conditions.
- **Frequency of Visit:** The team visits the AWCs and Schools in following frequencies:
 - Anganwari Centres: Twice in a year (Bi-annual)
 - Non-Residential Schools: Once in a year (Annual)
 - Residential Schools: Quarterly basis
- **Health Card:** After screening of the children the team issue a 'health card' for tracking of health status and future reference.

Facility Services:

- **New-born Screening at Facility level:** Head to Toe Screening of all delivered New-borns at all the Public Health Facilities (MCH/DHH/SDH/CHC/PHC) through Staff of Delivery Points. The Medical Officer and Staff Nurse are screening all the new-born babies from 'Head to toes' to identify the visible Birth Defects. The identified Birth Defect cases will be line listed and intimated to concern MHTs for early referral.
- **Assessment at District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC):** Confirmation of PF (preliminary findings), treatment/management including follow up of screened children and providing referral support up to superspeciality care, District Early

Intervention Centre (DEIC) is established which is the centre of all management/therapeutic/treatment activities and acting as a treatment hub by providing different referral linkages to different health facilities viz. secondary/tertiary level hospitals (Empanelled Pvt/Govt.).

- **Composition:** DEIC is having a team of 14 qualified technical personnels i.e. Paediatric Specialist, Medical Officer (MBBS), Dental Doctor, Optometris, Physiotherapist, Audiologist & Speech Therapist, Psychologist, t, Early Interventionist cum Special Educator, Social Worker, Staff Nurse, Lab Technician, Dental Technician, RBSK Manager and Data Entry Operator who work under one roof and provide a complete package of services.
- **Screening Modalities:** All the Specialist (Medical Officer and therapists) screen the referred children during the 1st visit to DEIC to find out the undiagnosed health issues. Subsequently, concerned Department follow-up with related Health Conditions. DEIC works in a team approach.
- The Specialist also visit SNCU, Pediatric Ward, Maternity Ward for routine health check-up of new-born and high-risk children and identification of visible Birth Defects.
- The RBSK manager is managing the linkage of tertiary care institutions (Government and empanelled Private institutions) for ensuring required referral support.
- **Referral to Specialized Health care institutions**
- Different Government and Private Health Care Institutions are empanelled under RBSK. The children who require further diagnosis for confirmation of disease are being referred to those institutions.

Government Institutions:

Sl. No.		Health Conditions
1	Old State Govt MCHs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCB MCH Cuttack • MKCG Berhampur • VIMSAR MCH Burla • SVPPGIP Cuttack 	All health Conditions i.e. Pediatric Surgery, Plastic Surgery, Eye Defects, Orthopedic, Neuro, Cardiac, and other critical care
2	Central Government Institutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AIIMS Bhubaneswar • Swami Vivekanand National Institute of Rehabilitation Training and Research (SVNIRTAR) 	Pediatric Surgery/medicine, Eye defect, Neuro, ENT, Cardiac, Ortho General Orthopedic, Clubfoot, Motor Delay, Neuro- Motor Impairment
3	Private Hospitals empanelled under RBSK <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narayana Hrudayalaya Limited (6 Hospitals) • Satya Sai Heart Hospital, Ahmedabad, Gujrat • LV Prasad Eye Institute, Bhubaneswar • Cure International India Trust (CIIT) 	Cardiac Ailments Eye Defects including RoP Clubfoot
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smile Train India • Mission Smile • Heritage Hospital 	Cleft lip & Palate

Implementation of RBSK :

Implementation Mechanism :

Frequency of visit of MHTs-RBSK:

In entire year to cover-

- Each AWC- Twice in a year (Bi-annually)
- Non-Residential Schools- Once in a year (Annual)
- Each Residential School- Quarterly basis
- Headquarter- Block CHC. Each MHT has been allocated specific coverage area for screening purpose.

Microplan for visit of MHTs-RBSK:

Annual Microplan of 28 nos. of MHTs-RBSK engaged in 14 of Blocks has been uploaded in district website www.koraput.nic.in.

The screenshot shows the website koraput.nic.in with the 'DOCUMENTS' menu selected. The page title is 'Annual Report'. A search filter is set to 'Annual Report'. A table lists the following documents:

Title	Date	View / Download
Annual Microplan of MHTs-RBSK Koraput for 2023-24 from CDMO, Koraput .	27/04/2023	View (4 MB)
Annual report of BMW from DHH,Jevpore .	11/01/2022	View (1 MB)

Review of Literature

With more than 400 million children under the age of 18, India is the country with the greatest number of children worldwide. At least 10% of preschoolers experience developmental delays, which keep them from growing to their full potential. Research on the frequency of disability and its correlation with sociodemographic characteristics and life satisfaction could yield important insights for improving the way health and social welfare institutions handle illnesses. The discussion that wraps up the study considers the efficacy of the quick cycle assessment methodology utilised, as well as the functional status of district early intervention centres (DEICs) in India and identifies any weaknesses in their referral system.

A preliminary search of the chosen literature revealed three major themes in recent work on early childhood intervention systems. The first theme discussed how impaired children fared in early intervention settings, how to lessen impairment, and how society views childhood handicap. Early intervention policies and programmes that are centred were the subject of the second theme. Practise that is trauma-informed was the third theme. The study of childhood trauma did not focus on any one kind of trauma; rather, it examined how societal elements like racism, poverty, and colonisation affected the lives of young children who were exposed to these problems.

In low- and middle-income nations, a small number of culturally sensitive developmental screening instruments have been proven effective for children under the age of five. Prioritising research should be given to updating current screening instruments in various ethnic and cultural contexts and then validating the results with normative significance.

RBSK Programme offered a useful framework for MHTs to conduct early screenings of children aged 0 to 18 for a variety of health issues, as well as for DEIC workers to monitor and support children who were referred to them. Numerous studies conducted in various states revealed that 42% of MHT and DEIC posts were unfilled. These must be completed in order to make the program's execution more sustainable and effective. Because there were no qualified Ophthalmologists available, retinalopathy of prematurity (ROP) could not be screened. The lack of a blood testing facility for haemoglobin electrophoresis prevented screening for sickle cell disease and thalassemia.

Referral services and follow-up to tertiary care centres should be expedited and streamlined in order to support early newborn screening at delivery sites. Additionally, referrals of SNCU discharged babies to DEIC require additional support and capacity building for healthcare providers. In a particular study, parents of children referred to DEICs were interviewed and their reasons for dissatisfaction were analysed. Of these, 36% mentioned that there was too much paperwork, while 55.3% felt that the exercise was pointless because specialised tests or treatment were not available at the DEIC.

Additionally, 73.4% of parents stated that losing their daily income would discourage them from visiting the DEIC on a regular basis for follow-up. Because of this, in locations where higher investigations are not available in government facilities, a provision should be in place to have them completed in private facilities at government-fixed rates, paid for by RBSK, and without incurring any costs to the children.

Every infant released from the SNCU needs to be line-listed and monitored in the community for routine follow-up in order to screen for health issues early and intervene sooner for a better result. There are several ways to track someone, including using the mother and child tracking system (MCTS), community health workers, ASHA, AWW, and SMS on mobile phones. Additionally, there is a pressing need to empower child carers in order to provide early stimulation, responsive health, and access to medical facilities at early stage of any delay or defect in development. All stakeholders in the multisystem approach must communicate in both directions in order to refer cases and establish connections at every level of management. Because public health facilities are still unable to assess, manage, or treat illnesses and developmental delays, carers are forced to seek out private sector diagnostics. According to one study, the average amount of money that carers had to pay out-of-pocket for their child with 2Ds—birth defects and developmental delay—was INR 45,000, but some carers had to spend as much as INR 950,000. Carers are discouraged by the OOP from pursuing additional management and referral services. Rather than receiving the essential care and free treatment as outlined in the RBSK, carers frequently face stress on a physical, psychological, and financial level. All team members, who are the cornerstones of DEIC development, must participate in capacity building of skills for the evaluation at DEICs.

There is also room for uniformity in the reporting of data on children with disabilities and delayed development at the national level. Consequently, an effort has been made to carry out a micro-level cross-sectional case study in order to evaluate the developmental status of early childhood in an all-encompassing way.

The continuum of care offered by RBSK services, which spans from birth to age 18, is what makes them special. In order to effectively address the various morbidities that are screened for, the health sector must prioritise the following: highly skilled labour; frequent training of community health workers about these screenings; early stimulation; follow-up; and referrals to the best centre for intervention. Policy makers ought to take note of the fact that early intervention can lower the burden of disease and DALYs while also raising the standard of living for India's future generation.

Childhood diseases is the commonest health condition under 4D.

The positions of paediatrician, medical officer, dentist, physiotherapist, optometrist, and lab technician were all filled during the study period, according to an analysis of the human resources available in the DEIC. Throughout the study period, there were vacancies in the positions of dental hygienist and early interventionist. During the study period, the services of a psychologist and an audiologist/speech therapist were frequently unavailable, and previous posts had also mentioned a number of resignations and new appointments.

The treatment of children with disabilities like autism has benefited greatly from RBSK. Comprehensive recommendations were provided for the establishment of specialty therapies such as sensory integration therapy.⁷ The hospital's psychiatry department and the psychologist affiliated with the DEIC assisted in the diagnosis and treatment of all other developmental delays, including cognitive, language, behavioural, and learning disorders.

Every year, 64.3 birth defects are present in every thousand live births worldwide.¹ With roughly 26 million births annually, India will have the highest global rate of birth defects. The RBSK programme has started early detection and treatment of these birth defects, which will have a significant positive impact on our children's health.

Among the three Ds, the highest utilisation rate belonged to those with birth defects. On the other hand, the majority of non-users had deficiencies. It might be because defects are typically either obvious or interfere with a child's daily routine, which prompts parents to seek services and reduces the amount of OOPE involved, whereas deficiencies are often not seen as a cause for concern by parents. According to a Pune study, service uptake for major anomalies such as congenital heart diseases and Congenital Talipes Equino Varus (CTEV) was good (up to 60%), whereas it was only about 17% for developmental disabilities. In this study, the combined uptake of RBSK services for developmental delays and defects was found to be approximately 32%.

Compared to non-users, there were more cases that were cured, undergoing treatment, or undergoing rehabilitation among service users. What is also important is the behaviour of seeking treatment. More than one-third of nonutilizers either stopped their treatment or did not visit a medical facility. It suggests that counselling is necessary following the issuance of the RBSK card in order to increase the use of RBSK services. The majority of these reluctant parents had children with SAM, and their stated excuses were: denial of a health problem; and lack of referral or contact from a health professional. or social and/or economic problems like superstition and wage loss. Similar explanations for non-treatment or non-compliance were reported in a Pune study. More than two thirds of those who were cured or receiving treatment or rehabilitation did so from private hospitals, demonstrating a preference for private healthcare facilities. This clear preference for private facilities has also been observed in other Indian studies on the behaviour of people seeking health care. The study's high and wildly fluctuating OOPE is cause for concern. This result is in good agreement with the preference for private providers.

Objectives :

Primay Objectives:

- **To know the effectiveness of DEIC-RBSK Programme in the district as it has been implemented since 2013-14.**
- **To know the improvement in screening**
- **Treatment/Management of 4D cases within the age group of 0-18 years.**

Secondary Objectives:

- **To findout the % of Client Satisfaction of 4D services provided by DEIC-RBSK Programme in the district**
- **To find the success of impact of RBSK programme programme**

Methodology

In this chapter, study methods have been throughly explained. The procedure used in selecting the participants, study design, study population, data collection and analysis etc.

3.2. Study Design

Cross Sectional:

Data Source: Routine data analysis to know the effectiveness of DEIC-RBSK Programme in the district.

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Quantitative data – Data collection (RBSK Software entry by Mobile Health Team, Health Management Information System & Stand-alone Monthly Progress Report of MHTs.

Client Satisfaction format – Qantitative Data collected through Google Form in online mode - To findout the % of Client Satisfaction of 4D services provided by DEIC-RBSK Programme in the district .

3.3. Study Area-

The study was performed in all the 14 blocks of Koraput district.

3.4. Study Population-

The population under the study included Mobile Health Teams-RBSK and Parents of 4D children who have undergone treatment/management supported by DEIC-RBSK Koraput.

3.5. Mode of Data Collection

The pre set questionnaire was prepared and collected through Google Form online mode.

All the Participants/Respondents were informed that participation in the study was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any stage if they wished. Each of the study participants was assured by the authors that the study findings would not have any impact on their job.

After completion, the questionnaires were rechecked for accuracy and completeness. Data from properly filled-in questionnaire was uploaded into excel sheet for analysis. There was no unutilized questionnaire.

3.6. Data Analysis and Presentation

The data was analyzed and results presented under each questionnaire in order to effectively answer the research questions. Figures, graphs and charts were also used to identify the trends and relationships in the data.

Some of the research findings about DEIC & RBSK Koraput:

1. Implementation of RBSK Web Application w.e.f. 01-04-2023

A central RBSK software has been developed by NIC, GoI for data analysis and report generation of RBSK activities. Accordingly, this district has also implemented entry in RBSK web portal by all 28 nos. of Mobile Health Teams w.e.f. 01-04-2023 on daily basis and status from Apr-23 to Oct-23 is mentioned as below:

Plan Recorded	DSS Closed	%age of DSS Closing	Total Screening	Total 4D Cases identified and Name wise entered	Referred
5320	5304	99.69%	352157	88120	87323

MHT wise Status from Apr-23 to Oct-23 as follows:

Sl. No.	Health Block	Mht_Name	Plan Recorded	Total Sceening	Total Cases	Referred
1	BANDHUGAON	MHT-1217	150	8473	1711	1711
2	BANDHUGAON	MHT-1218	111	7601	1098	1096
3	BOIPARIGUDA	MHT-12110	195	12683	3123	3110
4	BOIPARIGUDA	MHT-1219	168	11787	3427	3412
5	BORIGUMA	MHT-12111	257	15530	3555	3556
6	BORIGUMA	MHT-12112	230	15211	3608	3567
7	DASMANTAPUR	MHT-12114	189	11683	3089	3088
8	DASMANTAPUR	MHT-12115	190	9216	1862	1862
9	JEYPUR	MHT-12117	245	18575	3949	3895
10	JEYPUR	MHT-12121	214	18190	2985	2969
11	KORAPUT	MHT-12123	186	12325	2778	2755
12	KORAPUT	MHT-12124	242	17412	7580	7426
13	KOTPAD	MHT-12125	210	12307	3663	3655
14	KOTPAD	MHT-12126	163	12695	2965	2965
15	KUNDURA	MHT-1214	145	13885	2821	2722
16	KUNDURA	MHT-1215	171	12413	1557	1527
17	LAKSHMIPUR	MHT-12133	165	10485	2434	2385
18	LAKSHMIPUR	MHT-12134	149	9684	2741	2692
19	LAMTAPUT	MHT-12128	154	11116	2869	2841
20	LAMTAPUT	MHT-12129	198	9552	2857	2799
21	NANDAPUR	MHT-12135	238	16650	3939	3939
22	NANDAPUR	MHT-12136	235	14294	4176	4170
23	NARAYANPATNA	MHT-12137	136	7048	2095	2095
24	NARAYANPATNA	MHT-12138	104	5510	1599	1575
25	POTTANGI	MHT-12139	198	12364	3067	3047
26	POTTANGI	MHT-12140	152	12234	1942	1849
27	SEMILIGUDA	MHT-12130	276	18111	6112	6066
28	SEMILIGUDA	MHT-12131	249	14945	4518	4491
Total			5320	351979	88120	87265

2. Year Wise Achievement in Screening by MHTs-RBSK Koraput

Sl No	Year	AWC (0-6 year)			School (6-18 year)			Total Children (0-18 years)		
		Target	Ach.	%age	Target	Ach.	%age	Target	Ach.	%age
1	2014-15	140000	61831	44%	196736	160521	82%	336736	222352	66%
2	2015-16	234510	181436	77%	317107	308938	97%	551617	490374	89%
3	2016-17	269010	210800	78%	324012	319515	99%	593022	530315	89%
4	2017-18	289760	238465	82%	410810	398171	97%	700570	636636	91%
5	2018-19	244274	220703	90%	368169	313590	85%	612443	534293	87%
6	2019-20	244352	231305	95%	433402	423892	98%	677754	655197	97%
7	2020-21	244352	182661	75%	433402	185421	43%	677754	368082	54%
8	2021-22	275046	322144	117%	452569	474148	105%	727615	796292	109%
9	2022-23	273661	278982	102%	454714	473616	104%	728375	752598	103%
10	2023-24	143552	139636	97%	216763	191160	88%	360315	330796	92%

During 2020-21, due to Covid-19 and closure of all Schools/AWCs, screening activities were conducted only at villages, VHND/RI sessions observing Covid-19 norm by MHTs-RBSK from Nov-20 to Mar-21 and couldn't be possible from April-2020 to October-2020. Regular Monitoring was done by ADPHO(FW) through Virtual Mode. DEIC Staff were assigned to each MHTs and weekly review of DEIC staff was done by ADPHO(FW), Koraput.

3. Ach. in Institution Covered (AWC & School) by MHTs Apr-Sept 23

Period	AWC			AWC		
	Tar.	Ach	%age	Tar.	Ach	%age
Apr-Sept-2023	3264	3092	95%	1738	1666	96%

4. Identification of 4D by MHTs (2023-24) Apr-Sept

Screening - AWC	Screening - School	Total Screening	Name of 4D	4D	%age
139636	191160	330796	Birth_Defects	1082	0.77%
			Deficiencies	24172	7.31%
			Diseases	38990	11.79%
			Dev_Delays	4209	3.01%
			Ado_Concerns	3175	1.66%
			Others	3891	1.18%
			Total	75519	22.83%

5. Identification of Birth Defect at Delivery Points- Apr-Sept 23

Screening of Birth Defects at Labour Rooms/SNCUs of DHH, SDH and all Delivery Points.

Live Birth	Screening for Birth Defect	Birth Defect Identification at DP	%age of Birth Defect
12249	12249	404	3.30%

6. Year Wise Management/Treatment under RBSK Koraput

Sl. No.	Year	Children screened	Children Found with 4D	Children Treated / Managed	%age of Management
1	2014-15	222352	85126	74652	88%
2	2015-16	490374	129630	93166	72%
3	2016-17	530317	97009	73186	75%
4	2017-18	636636	91289	73612	81%
5	2018-19	534293	86450	74365	86%
6	2019-20	655197	112640	104296	93%
7	2020-21	368082	71766	61344	85%
8	2021-22	796292	196583	179871	91%
9	2022-23	752598	235392	219317	93%
10	2023-24	330796	75519	70919	94%

7. Achievement in DEIC vrs Tertiary Level Referral

Sl. No	Year	DEIC Referral & Management	Tertiary Level Referral & Management
1	2014-15	690	0
2	2015-16	3309	134
3	2016-17	5457	127
4	2017-18	10128	180
5	2018-19	10314	188
6	2019-20	11899	197
7	2020-21	6709	83
8	2021-22	10901	417
9	2022-23	13119	669
10	2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	8377	339
Cumulative		80903	2334

Sl. No.	Name of the Block CHC	Till March-2023	MKCG RMDPR	SCB, Cuttack	Sishu Bhawan Cuttack	SBM CUTTACK	NIRTAR,	AIMS, RRSR	LVPEI BBSR	Sai Janani BBSR	SRCC Mumbai	Aaradhya Tevnore	Kalinga Hosnital	Others	Total 2023-24	Cumulative
1	Bandhugaon	75	1		1		1		2		1		1		7	82
2	Boipariguda	133		2	2	2			4		2	1	1		14	147
3	Boriguma	259	1	13		2	2	1	23	1		2	2		47	306
4	Dasmantpur	169	4	5	1	2	2		7	2			2	3	28	197
5	Jeypore	214	5		3	1	5	2	14		2	3	3		38	252
6	Koraput	250	10	3	2		6	3	9	1	1	3	1		39	289
7	Kotpad	92	2		1	2		1	9	1			1	1	18	110
8	Kundra	99	1	4		1	2	1	8		2	1			20	119
9	Lamtaput	73		3	1			3	2	1		2	2		14	87
10	Laxmipur	58	3	1		2			4	1		1		1	13	71
11	Nandapur	153	1	2	2	2		1	8		1	2	2		21	174
12	Narayanpatna	72	2	5	1	1		1	4			1	1	3	19	91
13	Pottangi	154		7	3	2	1		5	1		5		1	25	179
14	Semiliguda	194	1	5	6	4	3		9	1	1	2	3	1	36	230
TOTAL		1995	31	50	23	21	22	13	108	9	10	23	19	10	339	2334

Tertiary Level Institutions are : SCB MCH Cuttack, Sishu Bhawan Cuttack, MKCG MCH Berhampur, AIIMS Bhubaneswar, Narayan Superspeciality Hospitals Kolkata/ Howrah/ Bangalore, Sri Sathya Sai Heart Hospital Ahmedabad, SBM Hospital Cuttack & Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar (SMILE TRAIN), SVNIRTAR Olatpur Cuttack, LV Prasad Eye Institute Bhubaneswar etc.

All eligible children with age appropriate 4D categories have been referred to the higher centres for proper treatment & management.

8. Referral of SAM Cases to NRC by MHTs-RBSK

Three nos. of NRCs are functioning in the district: SLN MCH Koraput, CHC Rabanaguda and CHC Laxmipur. Mobile Health Teams are identifying and referring the SAM cases to the NRCs.

Every year, above 70% of Admissions in three NRCs are being referred by MHTs-RBSK. During Apr-2023 to Sept-23, status of total admissions vrs referral by MHT-RBSK is stated below:

NRC Ravanaguda		NRC Koraput		NRC Laxmipur		Total		%age of referral by RBSK
Total Admission	Referred by RBSK							
147	112	184	155	136	76	467	343	73%

Sl. No	Name of the CHC	Total NRC Referral by RBSK till March 2023	STATUS OF NRC REFERRAL BY RBSK APR-23 to Sept-23									Cumulative
			NRC Ravanaguda		NRC Koraput		NRC Laxmipur		Total NRC Referral		%age	
1	Jeypore	344	54	36	2	0	0	0	56	36	64%	380
2	Nandapur	232	0	0	40	36	0	0	40	36	90%	268
3	Bandhugaon	231	0	0	2	1	26	25	28	26	93%	257
4	Boriguma	177	48	42	3	0	0	0	51	42	82%	219
5	Pottangi	199	0	0	18	16	0	0	18	16	89%	215
6	Kotpad	173	21	14	1	1	0	0	22	15	68%	188
7	Kundra	167	9	6	3	3	0	0	12	9	75%	176
8	Koraput	139	0	0	36	32	0	0	36	32	89%	171
9	Narayanpatna	139	0	0	1	0	17	17	18	17	94%	156
10	Dasantpur	121	0	0	30	27	2	2	32	29	91%	150
11	Semiliguda	104	0	0	37	31	0	0	37	31	84%	135
12	Boipariguda	119	15	14	2	0	0	0	17	14	82%	133
13	Laxmipur	89	0	0	0	0	91	32	91	32	35%	121
14	Lamtaput	60	0	0	9	8	0	0	9	8	89%	68
TOTAL		2294	147	112	184	155	136	76	467	343	73%	2637

9. Distribution of Hearing Aids at DEIC

Mobile Health Teams are identifying suspected Hearing Impairment cases and bringing to DEIC for confirmation by Audiologist through Bera/Audiometry Test. After confirmation, children are being provided with Hearing Aid as per their requirement i.e. Moderate, Severe or Profound category.

Sl. No.	Name of the CHC	Till 2022-23	Apr-23 to Sept-23	Cumulative
1	Koraput	75	2	77
2	Sunabeda Deaf School	74		74
3	Boriguma	65	2	67
4	Nandapur	53	4	57
5	Kotpad	46	1	47
6	Boipariguda	46		46
7	Jeypore	44	1	45
8	Dasmantpur	42	1	43
9	Semiliguda	40		40
10	Lamtaput	28	2	30
11	Bandhugaon	24	5	29
12	Kundra	26		26
13	Narayanpatna	20	1	21
14	Pottangi	19	1	20
15	Laxmipur	18		18
TOTAL		620	20	640

10. Treatment of Club Foot – DEIC RBSK Koraput

- Treatment of Club Foot cases at SLN MCH Koraput within the age group of 0-2 years.
- Treatment of Club Foot Cases at SVNIRTAR, Olatpur Cuttack >2 years upto 18 years.
- Corrective Surgery Camps organised at Koraput by the Team of Specialists of SVNIRTAR Olatpur Cuttack supported by SSEPD Deptt. Koraput. In a single camp more than 30 cases are being operated.

Sl. No.	Name of the Block	Apr-23 to Sept-23	Cumulative
1	Koraput	2	62
2	Jeypore	1	50
3	Boriguma	3	46
4	Semiliguda	0	38
5	Nandapur	3	34
6	Kotpad	1	31
7	Dasmantpur	2	27
8	Boipariguda	0	27
9	Lamtaput	0	18
10	Pottangi	0	18
11	Kundra	1	17
12	Laxmipur	1	13
13	Bandhugaon	0	13
14	Narayanpatna	0	11
15	Other District	13	170
TOTAL		27	575

11. Surgery of Cleft Lip & Cleft Palate Cases through RBSK

- Treatment of “Cleft Lip & Cleft Palate” cases are conducting free of cost at SBM Hospital (Plastic Surgery Deptt.), Cuttack, Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar etc.
- Tie-up is made with SMILE TRAIN and Mission SMILE for free treatment of such children

Sl. No.	Name of the CHC	2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	Total Cumulative
1	Semiliguda	4	45
2	Boriguma	2	33
3	Nandapur	3	33
4	Jeypore	3	31
5	Dasmantpur	2	29
6	Koraput	1	26
7	Pottangi	2	24
8	Kotpad	3	22
9	Lamtaput	0	18
10	Laxmipur	3	17
11	Boipariguda	2	15
12	Narayanpatna	2	15
13	Bandhugaon	0	14
14	Kundra	1	6
TOTAL		28	328

12. Management of identified Eye defect cases

Treatments of Congenital Cataract cases, RoP Cases, Vision Impairment cases and other eye related cases at hospital viz. LV Prasad Eye Institute, Bhubaneswar are conducting free of cost supported by RBSK and BSKY.

Sl. No.	Name of the CHC	Till 2022-23	2023-24	Cumulative
1	Bandhugaon	19	3	22
2	Boipariguda	30	4	34
3	Boriguma	122	23	145
4	Dasmantpur	39	7	46
5	Jeypore	47	16	63
6	Koraput	61	10	71
7	Kotpad	14	10	24
8	Kundra	42	8	50
9	Lamtaput	8	2	10
10	Laxmipur	8	4	12
11	Nandapur	47	12	59
12	Narayanpatna	25	5	30
13	Pottangi	51	5	56
14	Semiliguda	30	10	40
TOTAL		543	119	662

13. Management of CHD cases – DEIC RBSK

- Paed. Heart Surgery at Sri Sathya Sai Heart Hospital Ahmedabad, Narayan Hrudalaya Hospitals at Kolkata/Howrah/Jamshedpur. Also conducted Heart Surgery at SCB MCH Cuttak & Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar with the support of BSKY

Sl. No.	Name of the Block CHC	Management during Apr-23 to Sept-23			Total Management (Cumulative)		
		Medicine Mgmt	Surgery	Total Mgmt	Medicine Mgmt	Surgery	Total Mgmt
1	Ravanaguda	4	3	7	16	25	41
2	Mathalput	0	2	2	17	16	33
3	Lamtaput	0	2	2	13	17	30
4	Boipariguda	3	1	4	10	19	29
5	Kunduli	3	2	5	12	17	29
6	Dasmantpur	1	2	3	15	12	27
7	Pottangi	0	0	0	4	18	22
8	Nandapur	1	2	3	11	9	20
9	Borigumma	1	2	3	11	9	20
10	Laxmipur	1	0	1	11	5	16
11	Kotpad	1	1	2	5	10	15
12	Kundra	1	1	2	3	8	11
13	Narayanpatna	0	1	1	2	4	6
14	Bandhugaon	1	1	2	1	4	5
Total		17	20	37	131	173	304

14. Block Level Follow-up Therapy Camps for delay development children

Block Early Intervention camps are being conducted to those delay development children who are not coming to DEIC or leftout or missed children in distant blocks ensuring Home Based Therapy by the staff of DEIC. Nine numbers of identified CHCs viz. Bandhugaon, Laxmipur, Dasmantpur, Kotpad, Boipariguda, Borigumma, Lamtaput, Pottangi & Kunduli CHCs are the major focus points.

Sl. No	Year	Numbers of Therapeutic Camps organised	No. of 4D Children
1	2016-17	11	1548
2	2017-18	39	3297
3	2018-19	12	537
4	2019-20	20	1295
5	2021-22	4	239
6	2022-23	4	244
7	2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	7	491
Total		97	7651

15. RoP Screening and Management

- Ret Cam equipment has been supplied by RBSK Odisha to DEIC Koraput which is now installed at DHH Jeypore for screening of Ratinopathy of Prematurity (RoP) cases.
- Also DEIC-RBSK Koraput is organising RoP Screening camps at SLN MCH Koraput on every month. with the support of LVEPI Bhubaneswar,

Year	Screened
2019-20	66
2020-21	18
2021-22	51
2022-23	220
Total Screening	355
Referral	11

Month	ROP Screened	Identified & Referred	Treated
Apr-23	6	1	1
May-23	31	3	3
Jun-23	54	2	1
Aug-23	62	3	2
Sep-23	46	2	2
Oct-23	46	1	
Total Screening	245	12	9

16. Screening of HB (AMLAN) by MHTs at Res. Sch. (Apr-Sept)

Anaemia Mukta Laqshya AbhiyaN (AMLAN) was launched by Hon'ble Chief Minister of Odisha on 23-11-2022 throughout the State and since then continuing T3 campaign (Test, Treat & Talk) observing due norm. Mobile Health Teams under RBSK are estimating HB at Tribal Residential Schools and their performance as per attendance in Schools from Apr-23 to Sept-23 is as below:

Residential Schools			Children for Screening			Total Anaemic identified	
Target	Covered	%age	Target	Covered	%age	Identified	%age
368	338	92%	75269	59893	80%	32886	55%

Sl. No.	Name of the Block & MHT	Screening Outcome at Residential Schools under AMLAN				
		Children identified with Mild anemia	Children identified with Moderate anemia	Children identified with Severe anemia	Total Anaemic Children identified	%age of Anaemic
1	Borigumma MHT-II	566	155	26	747	71%
2	Pottangi MHT-I	1201	564	48	1813	68%
3	Dasmantpur MHT-II	1349	321	24	1694	65%
4	Kunduli MHT-II	1610	523	105	2238	65%
5	Pottangi MHT-II	2811	1376	5	4192	64%
6	Mathalput MHT-II	2428	812	32	3272	63%
7	Ravanaguda MHT-I	2428	812	32	3272	63%
8	Nandapur MHT-II	746	458	16	1220	63%
9	Ravanaguda MHT-II	1667	533	18	2218	63%
10	Boipariguda MHT-I	281	383	2	666	63%
11	Laxmipur MHT-II	708	312	4	1024	62%
12	Nandapur MHT-I	1202	377	15	1594	62%
13	Narayanpatna MHT-I	465	444	4	913	60%
14	Kunduli MHT-I	1316	372	62	1750	58%
15	Lamtaput MHT-I	462	153	11	626	57%
16	Mathalput MHT-I	53	159	25	237	56%
17	Kundra MHT-II	287	53	59	399	55%
18	Bandhugaon MHT-I	132	30	13	175	54%
19	Laxmipur MHT-I	646	597	9	1252	50%
20	Dasmantpur MHT-II	192	222	2	416	45%
21	Lamtaput MHT-II	452	235	4	691	42%
22	Boipariguda MHT-II	482	225	7	714	39%
23	Borigumma MHT-I	1094	391	14	1499	37%
24	Kundra MHT-I	56	25	13	94	9%
25	Kotpad MHT-II	54	17	8	79	4%
26	Kotpad MHT-I	50	27	14	91	4%
27	Bandhugaon MHT-II	0	0	0	0	0%
28	Narayanpatna MHT-II	0	0	0	0	0%
District Total		22738	9576	572	32886	55%

17. Tour Days (Screening only) & Daily Screening Average by MHTs (Apr-Sept-23)

Mobile Health Teams are visiting to AWCs and Schools in the frequency as mentioned below:

Status of Tour Days and Daily Screening Average of 28 nos. of MHTs-RBSK is as below

Tour Days (Screening only) by MHTs			Daily Screening Average by MHTs		
Target	Ach.	%age	Children Screened	Total Working Days	Daily Average
3061	3050	100	330796	2969	111

18. Average Case Load of DEIC :

- All 4Ds are being screened, managed/treated at DEIC.
 - DEIC Therapists are providing therapy services to the 4D children as per their need and also demonstrating to parents for Home based therapy on regular basis.
 - New cases and follow-up cases are being referred to DEIC by the MHTs and also self as advised by therapists.
 - Monthly Follow-up plans are prepared by concerned therapist.
- DEIC Case load of therapy children is as below:

Sl No	Year	Other Conditions Managed through DEIC	No. of Developmental Delay Children provided therapeutic intervention
1	2014-15	690	136
2	2015-16	3309	783
3	2016-17	5457	2232
4	2017-18	10128	1745
5	2018-19	10314	1979
6	2019-20	11899	496
7	2020-21	6709	242
8	2021-22	10901	310
9	2022-23	13119	442
10	2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	8377	946

28. Birth Defect Case Management at DP/SNCU/DEIC

Special New born Care Unit (SNCU) has been established at SLN MCH Koraput and DHH Jeypore with a provision of 24x7 services to sick newborns.

- Regular visit of DEIC staff (Physiotherapist, Audiologist, Social Worker) to SNCU Koraput alongwith Counseling on 4D for follow up activities of children. Also Audiologist is performing Berra test for the suspected hearing problem newborns.
- SNCU discharged children are being referred by SNCU staff to DEIC prior to discharge for assessment of all DEIC Therapists.
- Supply of Birth Defect Posters at each DP & SNCU
- ROP Screening –(RET CAM) has been supplied from RBSK Odisha to DHH Jeypore)

Sl. No.	Year	District Achievement			
		Total Live Birth	No of Children Screened Under New Born Screening	No of Children identified with Birth defect Under New Born Screening	%age of identification
1	2014-15	28352	0	9	0.00%
2	2015-16	27196	10376	47	0.45%
3	2016-17	24994	17082	56	0.33%
4	2017-18	26202	19721	66	0.33%
5	2018-19	27228	25956	79	0.30%
6	2019-20	25472	24834	188	0.76%
7	2020-21	26288	25374	169	0.67%
8	2021-22	28736	28736	244	0.85%
9	2022-23	25837	25837	342	1.32%
10	2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	12217	12217	411	3.36%

Year wise %age of identification

Sl. No.	Year	SNCU achievement			
		No of SNCU babies discharged	No of SNCU babies discharged by DEIC	No of SNCU discharged babies identified with Birth defect	%age of Screening
1	2014-15	873	0	9	0%
2	2015-16	964	17	33	2%
3	2016-17	797	265	44	33%
4	2017-18	1397	848	60	61%
5	2018-19	1752	1151	85	66%
6	2019-20	1757	1467	160	83%
7	2020-21	1516	1217	142	80%
8	2021-22	3045	2745	170	90%
9	2022-23	2751	2751	157	100%
10	2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	1469	1469	83	100%

Screening by DEIC- %age

These two types of Posters supplied from RBSK to each DP and SNCU for reference

29. Five Day Basic & Three Days Refresher Training of MHTs-RBSK by National Master Trainers:

For capacity building of Mobile Health Team members, Five Days Basic Training and Three Days Residential Refresher Training of MHTs-RBSK (AYUSH Doctors, Pharmacists & ANMs) of Districts Koraput, Raygada, Malkangiri, Bolangir, Ganjam & Nabarangpur was conducted at DTU, Koraput as per the scheduled below:

Year	Training	Batches	Koraput	Malkangiri	Gajapati	Nabarangpur	Raygada	Bolangir	Ganjam	Total
2016-17	5 days Basic	1	8	6				9	15	38
2019-20	5 days Basic	5	38	28	53	33				152
2020-21	3 days Refresher	8	45	30		45				120
2021-22	5 days Basic	8	29	19		24	47			119
2021-22	3 days Refresher	9	43	37		11	41			132
2023-24	5 days Basic	2	30	1		2	15			48
2023-24	3 days Refresher	1	10	5		8	7			30
Total		34	203	126	53	123	110	9	15	639

5 days Basic Training		3 days Refresher Training	
Batches completed	MHTs trained	Batches completed	MHTs trained
16	357	18	282

30. Monthly CME-cum-Review of MHTs-RBSK

For enhancing the working ability and gaining of latest knowledge, District level CME-cum-Review Meetings of Mobile Health Teams under RBSK and to the Service Providers (Medical Officer / Staff Nurse / ANM) at Delivery Points for Newborn Screening as per RBSK norm has been conducted as follows.

Year	No. of Review cum CME conducted for Capacity Building of MHTs-RBSK
2014-15	04
2015-16	19
2016-17	13
2017-18	09
2018-19	10
2019-20	09
2020-21	03 (Due to Covid-19, CME couldn't be conducted)
2021-22	10
2022-23	12
2023-24 (Apr-Sept)	06 (10-04-23, 25-04-2023, 30-05-2023, 05-08-2023, 29-08-2023, 16-09-2023)

Year	No. of CME conducted
2014-15 to Sept-23	95

31. District Core Committee Meeting with line departments.

District level Core Committee has been constituted under the Chairpersonship of Collector & DM, Koraput for proper functioning & monitoring of RBSK/RKSK activities with the members as stated below:

Sl. No.	Designation	Designation in Committee	Sl. No.	Designation	Designation in Committee
1	Collector & DM, Koraput	Chairperson	7	DEO, S&ME Koraput	Member
2	CDM&PHO	Co-Chairperson	8	DSWO, WCD Deptt.	Member
3	DPHO	Member	9	DWO, ST/SC Dev. Deptt.	Member
4	ADPHO(FW)	Member	10	DPM, NHM Koraput	Member
5	DMO(MS)-cum-Suptd. DHH	Member	11	DMRCH	Member
6	Paed. Spl. DHH	Member	12	RBSK Manager	Member

Year	No. of Meetings conducted
2014-15 to Sept-23	26

Year	Meetings Conducted	Dates of the Meetings (Chaired by Collector & DM, Koraput)
2014-15	3	12.06.2014, 31.01.2015, 27.03.2015
2015-16	4	17.06.2015, 21.11.2015, 20.02.2016, 19.03.2016
2016-17	3	16.07.16, 07.12.16, 18.03.17
2017-18	3	17.07.17, 06.11.17, 19.01.18
2018-19	4	21.05.18, 06.09.18, 27.12.18, 24.01.19
2019-20	2	30.08.19, 30.01.20
2020-21	2	26-02-2021, 01.03.2021
2021-22	1	08-07-2021
2022-23	3	25-11-2022, 28-02-2023, 28-03-2023
2023-24	1	07-09-2023

Review by Collector & DM, Koraput for RBSK, RKSK, School Health- AB Koraput on 07.09.2023

32. Co-ordination Meeting

District level Convergence Meeting with line department viz.H&FW, S&ME, SSD & W&CD has been conducted for proper functioning & monitoring of RBSK/RKSK activities with the members as stated below:

Year	No. of Meetings conducted
2018-19 to Sept-23	07

Year	No. of District Convergence meetings conducted
2018-19	01 (24-01-2019)
2019-20	01 (30-08-2019)
2020-21	01 (26-02-2021)
2021-22	01 (08-07-2021)
2022-23	02 (25-11-2022 & 28-02-2023)
2023-24	01 (30-10-2023)

Sl. No.	Members
1	CDM&PHO
2	ADPHO(FW), Koraput
3	DWO, ST/SC Dev. Deptt.
4	DSWO, W&CD Deptt.
5	DEO, S&ME Deptt.
6	DPM, NHM
7	RBSK-RKSK Manager
8	Block Education Officers, S&ME Deptt.
9	CDPOs, W&CD Deptt.
10	Welfare Extension Officers, SSD Deptt.
11	Block Programme Managers, NHM
12	MDM Co-ordinator, O/o-DEO, S&ME

34. Cardiac, Neuro & BMT Screening Camp at DHH Jeypore

Mission Director, NHM Odisha vide office letter No.11176 dd.22-09-2023 (Flag-A) had approved to organise Cardiac, Neuro & Thalassemia, Sickle Cell (for BMT) screening camp under RBSK at DHH Koraput at Jeypore in collaboration with SRCC Children's Hospital, Mumbai (a unit of Narayan Hrudalaya Limited) as detailed below:

Total Children attended in Cardiac, Neuro & BMT Camp at DHH Jeypore (27th & 28th Sept-23)

Sl. No.	Name of the MHT	Children Attended			
		Suspected CHD	Neuro & Epilepsy	Sickle cell & Thalassemia (BMT)	Total
1	Koarpur District	66	112	75	253
2	Malkangiri District	12	20	1	33
3	Raygada District	11	14	1	26
4	Nabarangpur District	14	16	5	35
Total		103	162	82	347

Confirmed Cases found during 2 days Camp (Cardiac, Neuro & Epilepsy and BMT) 27th to 28th Sept-23

Sl. No.	Date	Cardiac Cases		Neuro & Epilepsy		Sickle Cell & Thalassemia			
		Total Cases attended	Surgery for CHD	Total Cases attended	Medicine Prescribed & Therapy	Surgery	Total Cases attended	Needs Electrophoresis	Swab Collection done for BMT
1	27-09-2023	62	36	76	70	6	82	40	32
2	28-09-2023	41	21	86	80	6	0	0	0
Total		103	57	162	150	12	82	40	32

ଶିଶୁ ରୋଗ ଚିହ୍ନଟ ଶିବିର ଯୋଗଦେଲେ ମୁଖ୍ୟମନ୍ତ୍ରୀ ବିଶେଷଜ୍ଞ ଡାକ୍ତର

ଜୟପୁର, ୨୭ତା (ରୁ୍ୟରୋ): ଜିଲ୍ଲା ହସପିଟାଲରେ ଶିଶୁ ରୋଗ ଚିହ୍ନଟ ଶିବିର ଆରମ୍ଭ ହୋଇଛି । ୨ ଦିନ ଧରି ଚାଲିବାରୁ ଶିବା ଏହି ଶିବିରରେ ମୁଖ୍ୟମନ୍ତ୍ରୀ ବିଶେଷଜ୍ଞ ଡାକ୍ତରମାନେ ଯୋଗ ଦେଇଛନ୍ତି । ଅତି ୨୨୦ ଜଣଙ୍କ ଚିକିତ୍ସା କରାଯାଇଥିବା ତାଙ୍କରଖଣା ପତ୍ରପୁ ବୁଦନା ବିଆଯାଇଛି ।

ଆଜି ପୂର୍ବାହ୍ନରେ ଡିଏଚ୍-ଏଚ୍ ପରିସରରେ ଆରମ୍ଭ ହୋଇଥିଲା ଶିବିର । ଏହାର ଆୟୋଜକ ଶିବା ଜିଲ୍ଲା ସାମ୍ବଲ୍ ପମିଡି (କେଏସଏସଏସ), ରାଷ୍ଟ୍ରୀୟ ସ୍ୱାସ୍ଥ୍ୟ କାର୍ଯ୍ୟକ୍ରମ (ଆରବିଏସକେ) ଏବଂ ମୁଖ୍ୟମନ୍ତ୍ରୀ ଏସଆରସିସି ଶିଶୁ ହସପିଟାଲ (ନାରାୟଣ ହେଲ୍ଥ) । ସିଡିଏମଓ ତାଙ୍କର ଅଭିଷେକ କରାଯାଇଛି । ଶିଶୁଙ୍କ ହୃଦ ରୋଗ, ସ୍ୱାସ୍ଥ୍ୟରତ ସମସ୍ୟା, ମୁଣ୍ଡା (ଏପିଲେପ୍ସି) ଏବଂ ସିଜିଲ୍ ଏବଂ ଥାଲସେମିଆ ରୋଗୀଙ୍କ ବୋଧ ମ୍ୟାଗେ ଟ୍ରାନ୍ସଫୁଜେସନ୍ (ବିଏମ୍ଟି) ବନ୍ଦରେ ବିଶେଷଜ୍ଞ ଡାକ୍ତରମାନେ ଯାଞ୍ଚ କରିଥିଲେ । କୋରାପୁଟ ଜିଲ୍ଲା ୧୨୯, ମାଲକାନଗିରିର ୩୨, ନବରଙ୍ଗପୁରର ୩୩ ଏବଂ ରାୟଗଡ଼ା ଜିଲ୍ଲାର ୨୬ ଜଣ ଶିଶୁଙ୍କ ସାମ୍ବଲ୍ ପରୀକ୍ଷା କରାଯାଇଥିଲା । ରୁ୍ୟରୋ ଏବଂ ଏପିଲେପ୍ସି ବିଶେଷଜ୍ଞ ଡାକ୍ତର ପୁଞ୍ଜା ରାଉଫିଲ, ତାଙ୍କର ସୌରଭ ସାମନ୍ତରାୟ, ହୃଦ ରୋଗ ବିଶେଷଜ୍ଞ ଡାକ୍ତର ସୁପ୍ରତୀମ ସେନ, ବିଏମ୍ଟି ବିଶେଷଜ୍ଞ ଡାକ୍ତର ରୁଚିତ୍ସା ମିଶ୍ର, ଜିଓଗ୍ରାଫି ମୁଖ୍ୟ ପୁଞ୍ଜାବାଲ ବଳିଆରାୟ, ଏବଂ ଏଚ୍ ପରିଚାଳକ ଅମିତ କେରକର ପ୍ରମୁଖ ଏଥିରେ ଯୋଗ ଦେଇଥିଲେ । ଅନ୍ୟମାନଙ୍କ ମଧ୍ୟରେ ଏସ୍ଡିଏଚ୍ ଅଧ୍ୟକ୍ଷକ ଡାକ୍ତର ରାମଚନ୍ଦ୍ର ମହାନ୍ତି, ଏନଏଚ୍ଏମ୍ ଜିଲ୍ଲା କାର୍ଯ୍ୟକ୍ରମ ମ୍ୟାଗେଜର ଶୁଭକାନ୍ତ ରାୟଚନ୍ଦ୍ର, ହସପିଟାଲ ମ୍ୟାଗେଜର ରୁପସା ମାଧୁମିତା ନାୟକ, ଡିଆଇଜି ଡାକ୍ତର, ଆରବିଏସକେ ମ୍ୟାଗେଜର ବିଶ୍ୱ ରଞ୍ଜନ ମୁଖ ପ୍ରମୁଖଙ୍କ ସହ ଆରବିଏସକେ ମୋବାଇଲ୍ ହେଲ୍ଥ ଟିମ୍, ଡିଆଇଇସି କର୍ମଚାରୀ ଏଥିରେ ସହଯୋଗ କରିଥିଲେ ।

ଜେଲ୍ ଗଲେ ୨ ମୋବାଇଲ୍ ଡାକ୍ତର ବାକ୍ସ ଜବତ, ଫୋନ୍ ଉଦ୍ଧାର

34. Surgery of 28 nos. of Club Foot children under RBSK supported by SSEPD Koraput at DHH Jeypore

Club Foot Corrective Surgery Camp was conducted at DHH Jeypore by the team of Specialists of SVNIRTAR, Olatpur Cuttack from dtd.10-01-2023 to 12-01-2023 supported by RBSK and SSEPD Koraput.

Mobile Health Teams under RBSK had referred 95 nos. of Club Foot cases identified by them at different AWCs and Schools. Transportation of children and their attendants from their doorstep to DHH Jeypore was provided in MHT vehicles free of cost under RBSK. After preliminary screening by the team of SVNIRTAR, 28 nos. of such cases were admitted at DHH Jeypore for required surgery and rest cases will be conducted surgery in phased manner.

After surgery, all children were stayed at DHH Jeypore for 21 days for necessary follow up by Specialist of DHH Jeypore.

1st Plaster removal and re-plaster done on 1st Feb-23 at DHH Jeypore and all 21 nos. of children were drop back to their home in MHT-RBSK vehicles. Within the said duration, children were being followed up by the MHTs-RBSK at their doorstep and required medication was provided to them as per need.

Again Plaster Removal camp was conducted at DDRC Koraput on 10th and 11th Mar-2023 and Mobile Health Teams-RBSK brought the 28 nos. of children from their doorstep to Koraput in MHT-RBSK Vehicles. On the same day, all the children were provided with Surgical Shoe at DDRC Koraput supported by SSEPD Koraput and drop back to their home in MHT vehicles.

Now all the operated children are in good condition and able to walk as normal human being.

Club Foot Children on 10-01-2023 for screening

Block wise numbers of Club Foot children operated as follows:

Sl. No.	Name of the Block	Jan-23
1	Semiliguda	5
2	Bandhugaon	4
3	Nandapur	3
4	Kundra	3
5	Narayanpatna	3
6	Jeypore	2

Sl. No.	Name of the Block	Jan-23
7	Kotpad	2
8	Boipariguda	2
9	Dasmantpur	2
10	Koraput	1
11	Boriguma	1
TOTAL		28

Photograph during 1st Plaster Removal and Re-Plaster on 01-02-2023 at DHH Jeypore:

Photograph during 2nd Plaster Removal and Shoe distribution on 10-03-2023 & 11.03.23 at DDRC Koraput

Detail of one child as mentioned below:

**Name : Laxman Khoda, S/o- Bhima Khoda, At/Po- Goliput, PS- Nandapur,
6 yr/MCH, Right CTEV.**

**Mobile Health Team-I, RBSK
CHC Nandapur has visited the
house of Laxman Khoda to
counsel and to bring for
surgery. After Club Foot
Corrective surgery, Surgical
Shoe was provided to the child
and MHT also followed at
doorstep.**

**Now the child is wearing the
shoe regularly and able to walk
properly.**

**YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF AUDIOLOGY & SPEECH THERAPY DEPARTMENT,
DEIC KORAPUT FROM 2013-14 TO 2023-24**

Sl. No.	Year	Case Load				No. of delay cases improved/cured after intervention at DEIC	No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room	No. of Success story submitted by the staff	No of children identified with hearingdefeact under new born screening at SNCU	No of children identified with hearingdefeact under new born screening at Labour
		Total Case Load	Total Working	Daily Average	Monthly Average						
1	2013-14	140	35	4	120	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	NA	NA	NA
2	2014-15	850	238	4	70	55	170	18	NA	NA	NA
3	2015-16	918	230	4	76	70	210	20	3	NA	NA
4	2016-17	1980	240	8	165	210	170	25	8	NA	NA
5	2017-18	5352	233	23	446	414	820	1228	19	18	4
6	2018-19	3180	125	25	265	70	702	1151	10	4	5
7	2019-20	5743	246	23	478	148	1343	1547	20	17	15
8	2020-21	4223	221	19	352	88	1163	950	10	16	5
9	2021-22	-NA-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
10	2022-23	724	63	12	242	93	240	74	2	2	NA
11	2023-24	2142	141	15	306	213	998	718	11	10	2

**YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY DEPARTMENT, DEIC KORAPUT
FROM 2013-14 TO 2023-24**

Sl. No.	Year	Case Load				No. of delay cases improved/cured after intervention at DEIC	No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room	No. of Success story submitted by the staff
		Total Case Load	Total Working Days	Daily Average	Monthly Average				
1	2013-14	154	39	4	-NA-	NA	NA	NA	NA
2	2014-15	1251	248	5	104	76	187	15	NA
3	2015-16	1524	252	6	127	89	221	16	5
4	2016-17	2590	260	10	216	239	180	22	9
5	2017-18	3678	252	15	307	568	317	35	21
6	2018-19	3295	256	13	275	416	300	32	15
7	2019-20	3075	245	13	256	306	299	30	16
8	2020-21	2596	240	11	216	253	1005	75	11
9	2021-22	-NA-	-NA-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
10	2022-23	277	70	4	92	10	152	21	1
11	2023-24	1904	149	13	272	172	925	63	7

**YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF PSYCHOLOGY DEPARTMENT, DEIC KORAPUT
FROM 2013-14 TO 2023-24**

Sl. No.	Year	Case Load				No. of delay cases improved/cured after intervention at DEIC	No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room	No. of Success story submitted by the staff
		Total Case Load	Total Working Days	Daily Average	Monthly Average				
1	2013-14	-NA-	-NA-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2	2014-15	-NA-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
3	2015-16	195	63	03	65	NA	125	23	NA
4	2016-17	1271	259	05	22	143	348	15	08
5	2017-18	2330	216	11	194	195	462	27	18
6	2018-19	2514	245	10	210	256	620	24	19
7	2019-20	1965	181	11	164	187	500	34	12
8	2020-21	1697	177	10	189	123	972	31	13
9	2021-22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
10	2022-23	260	84	3	65	NA	168	NA	1
11	2023-24	872	121	7	145	23	491	18	3

YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF DENTAL DEPARTMENT, DEIC KORAPUT FROM 2019-20 TO 2023-24

Sl. No	Year	Case Load				No. of cases improved/cured after intervention at DEIC	No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room
		Total Case Load	Total Working Days	Daily Average	Monthly Average			
1	2019-20	2168	276	8	166	2168	1103	0
2	2020-21	1792	274	6	138	1792	1238	37
2	2021-22	1928	260	7	160	1928	1096	42
2	2022-23	2352	258	8	196	2352	1087	49

**YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF SPECIAL EDUCATION DEPARTMENT, DEIC
KORAPUT
FROM 2013-14 TO 2020-21**

Sl. No.	Year	Case Load				No. of delay cases improved/cured after intervention at DEIC	No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room	No. of Success story submitted by the staff
		Total Case Load	Total Working Days	Daily Average	Monthly Average				
1	2013-14	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2	2014-15	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
3	2015-16	163	64	03	54	NA	120	13	NA
4	2016-17	822	259	03	68	89	238	13	04
5	2017-18	2220	239	09	185	99	397	15	10
6	2018-19	1989	247	08	166	194	151	25	14
7	2019-20	2160	224	09	180	116	276	23	15
8	2020-21	1975	243	08	164	159	726	50	10
9	2021-22	2070	240	8	172	10	931		5
10	2022-23	2110	247	8	176	12	1052		5
11	2023-24	1726	144	12	246	7	899		4

**YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF optometry DEPARTMENT, DEIC KORAPUT
FROM 2021-22 TO 2023-24**

**OPTOMETRIST, DEIC, RBSK KORAPUT,
SRI JYOTI RANJAN PANDA, doj-18-10-2021**

Sl. No.	Year	Case Load				RoP Cases				Cataract Cases			Other Eye Problem Cases			No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room	No. of Success story submitted by the staff
		Total Case Load	Total Working Days	Daily Average	Monthly Average	NO. OF NEWBORN Screened under	Identified	Referral	Treatment completed	Identified	Referral	Completed Treatment	Identified	Referral	Completed Treatment			
1	2021-22	1210	113	11	202	52	1	1	NA	23	23	18	76	76	52	364	116	5
2	2022-23	3114	239	13	259	135	5	5	3	23	23	20	151	151	140	947	283	8
3	2023-24	1941	145	14	277	244	12	12	11	23	23	18	207	207	180	877	152	10

**YEAR WISE PERFORMANCE OF occupational therapy DEPARTMENT, DEIC KORAPUT
FROM 2022-23 TO 2023-24**

**OCCUPATIONAL THERAPIST, DEIC, RBSK KORAPUT,
DR. RAKHEL KUMAR NAYAK, doj-26-12-2022**

Sl. No.	Year	Case Load				No. of delay cases improved/cured after intervention at DEIC	No. of SNCU discharge Babies screened	No. of New Born screened at Labour Room	No. of Success story submitted by the staff
		Total Case Load	Total Working Days	Daily Average	Monthly Average				
1	2022-23	550	68	8	183	17	265	27	2
2	2023-24	1797	141	13	150	55	983	93	8

Success Story of Salini Khora

Name of the Child : Salini Khora, FCH-3.4 yr

Address : Padua, BLOCK-Nandapur, DIST-

KoraputDisease : Delayed Development Milestone

Treated Institution : DEIC, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child came with complaints of difficulty in standing and walking 7 months back. She was having positive birth history of delayed birth cry and neonatal seizure. On

Examination: Poor dynamic trunk control, poor sit to stand abilities.

Therapy programme (w.e.f.:26.04.2023)- MAT activity, Dynamic trunk control exercise, gait training etc.

Post-Intervention condition :

Now the child is able to walk independently, able to clear obstacles and able to climb staircase.

The parents are happy with the therapy programme of DEIC, Koraput.

Success Story of Rasmi Khora

Name of the Child : Rasmi Khora, FCH-1.6 yr

Address : BLOCK-Koraput, DIST-Koraput

Disease : Delayed Developmental Milestone

Treated Institution: DEIC, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child came with complaints of difficulty in sitting, standing. O/O: Child was hyperirritable, not able to follow command. O/E: Poor trunk control, poor sitting balance.

Therapy program: MAT activity, sup to sit to stand training, trunk control exercise.

Pre-Intervention condition :

Now the child is able to sit independently and stand with support. The parents are happy with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Intervention Photograph

Post intervention Photograph

Success Story of Kailash Chandra Nayak

**Name of the Child : Kailash Chandra Nayak, MCH,
8 yrs Address : BLOCK-Borigumma, DIST-
Koraput**

**Disease : Left Hemiparesis
Treated Institution: DEIC, Koraput**

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child came with complaints of difficulty in using left upper and lower extremity, difficulty in walking properly. H/o: positive birth history. O/E: spasticity of left hip & knee extensor, elbow & wrist flexor.

Therapy program: NDT technique

Post-Intervention condition:

Balance and coordination improved while walking. Able to climb stairs with weight ball.

The parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC, RBSK.

Success Story of Tanushi Mali

Name of the Child : Tanushi Mali, FCH, 1.10 yrs

Address : BLOCK-Jeypore, DIST-Koraput

Disease : DDM Treated

Institution : DEIC, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child came with complaints of difficulty in standing and difficulty in walking independently. H/o: positive birth history. O/E: Tightness of B/L hamstring and weakness of left ankle everter.

Therapy program: Developmental therapy, Trunk control exercises.

Post-Intervention condition:

Now the child is able to stand independently with support from external objects. Trunk control improved.

The parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC, RBSK.

Success Story of Baijayanti Bhanja

Name of the Child : Baijayanti Bhanja, MCH, 2
yrsAddress : BLOCK-Kotpad, DIST-
Koraput

Disease : DDM

Treated Institution : DEIC, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child came with complaints of difficulty in sitting and standing. H/o: Delayed birth cry, HIE-II. O/O: Sits in “W” sitting posture. O/E: Poor trunk control and poor sitting balance. Spasticity of b/l hip flexor and knee extensor present.

Therapy program: Developmental therapy, sitting balance.

Post-Intervention condition:

Now the child is able to sit independently without support. Trunk control improved. Present therapy focuses on Standing balance and dynamic trunk control. The parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC,RBSK.

Success Story of Arav kumar saho

Name of the Child : Arav kumar saho (2.8yrs/M)
Father's Name : Rajesh kumar saho
Address : sunabeda, DIST-Koraput
Diagnosis : Spoken language disorder with ASD.
Therapist : Madhusmita Samantaray (Audiologist & speech language pathologist)
Therapy given : Speech therapy

Pre-Intervention condition:

Parents of the child came to DEIC with the complaint of unable to speak age appropriately and excessive exposure to gadgets. He is first issue to non-consanguinous parents.No significant medical and family history.

Receptive language- child is able to comprehend few lexical categories and kinship terms. He is follows basic commands.Understanding about emotions and negations.memory is good.

Expressive language- child is able to expresses few lexical categories and also able to expressing alphabets with words and counting up to /1-30/.

Present condition of the child :

Receptive language- Demonstrates some understanding by appropriate responses to such action words as 'sitdown', 'come here' etc. Demonstrates some understanding of distinctions in personal nouns such as 'give it to her' etc.understanding the meaning of most common verbs like 'eat', 'drink' etc.Recognizes names of familiar people and objects.Understand prepositions such as 'on', 'under', 'front' etc.

Expressive language- Childs MLU limited 2 to 3 words.He is able to express most of the lexical categories,common objects and rhymes with action.He is able to address parents most of the time and also says alphabets with words clearly and does counting up to 50.He is able to do need based communication using 2 words.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of child.

Success Story of Raj Kumar Nayak

Name of the Child : Raj Kumar(5yrs/M)
Father's Name : Banamali Nayak
Address : Borigumma, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Spoken language disorder with CI.
Therapist : Madhusmita Samantaray (Audiologist & speech language pathologist)

Pre-Intervention condition:

Parents of the child came to DEIC with the complaint of unable to hear and speak.

Diagnosis and Therapy Suggest:-

The test used:- OAE/BERA

The therapy suggested : Hearing aids fitted by DEIC,RBSK,koraput and speech therapy. Speech therapy continues after hearing aid fitting but there is no satisfactory result of the child.So, it is planning for cochlear implant of the child,the child refer to AIIMS, BHUANESWAR through DEIC,RBSK,koraput. Cochlear implantation of the child done on date 13/06/2023. Now he is hearing properly and continue speech therapy at DEIC,koraput.

Therapy Given by Speech Therapist:-

- Auditory verbal training
- Identification of lexical items
- Vocalization

Present condition of the child :

- He is able to respond after his name calling .
- He is able to comprehend and identify few lexical items like /fruits/, /bodyparts/, /alphabets/, /colours/ etc.
- Understanding about shades of emotions and nagations.
- The child is able to expresses some sounds like /aa/,/e/,/u/,/o/,/pa/,/ba/ etc. and also expressing family members like /papa/, /baba/, /mama/ etc.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement.

Success Story of Punyatoya Bisoi

Name of the Child : Punyatoya Bisoi, FCH-17 yr
Father's Name : Gurunath Bisoi
Address : Lima, BLOCK-Kundra, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Megalo Cornea
Treated Institution: LV Prasad Eye Institute Bhubaneswar

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was diagnosed by MHT-RBSK CHC Kundra and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput identified the diseases as Megalo Cornea and referred to higher centre for further treatment. Accordingly, she was referred to LV Prasad Eye Institute, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.213 dtd.20.01.2022 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Pre-Intervention condition :

The child was operated at LVPEI Bhubanswar on dtd.18.02.2022 free of cost through RBSK Odisha and the surgery is successful. Now the child will be able to see as a normal child.

The parents are happy with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Bablu Jani

Name of the Child : Bablu Jani, MCH-13 yr
Father's Name : Ramesh Jani
Address : Lima, BLOCK-Kundra, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Developmental Cataract (RE)
Treated Institution: LV Prasad Eye Institute Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr. Dipak, LVPEI BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was diagnosed by MHT-RBSK CHC Kundra and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput identified the diseases as Megalo Cornea and referred to higher centre for further treatment. Accordingly, she was referred to LV Prasad Eye Institute, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.213 dtd.20.01.2022 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Pre-Intervention condition :

The child was operated at LVPEI Bhubaneswar on dtd.07.02.2022 free of cost through RBSK Odisha and the surgery is successful. Now the vision of the child is as a normal child.

The parents are happy with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Asmit Kindo

Name of the Child : Asmit Kindo, 3years 8months, Male

Father's Name : P.K. Kindo

Address : HAL township, Sunabeda, BLOCK-Semiliguda, DIST-Koraput

Diagnosis: Mild ASD

Treated by : Occupational Therapist, DEIC, RBSK, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

Child came to occupational therapy with complains (from his parents) of No name call response, don't interact with peer groups, restless and speech difficulty. Then I did the assessment using SIPT module and found that he had multi-sensory defensiveness (only auditory seeking), poor attention span & sitting tolerance, poor fine motor & gross motor functions, ADLs difficulties and maldaptive behaviors.

Therapeutic Intervention:

After the problems identified I planned a weekly occupational therapy programme which includes; - sensory integration therapy, ball catching & throwing, swing activities, animal walks, different puzzle activities with peg board, brain gym, imitation activities and group therapy.

Post-Intervention condition:

After few months of therapy, the child shows a remarkable improvement in attention span and sitting tolerance, reduced tactile defensive issues, now follows all instructions with proper response to name call and due to group therapy peer group interaction also improved little bit.

The parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC, RBSK.

Success Story of Piyush Golari

Name of the Child :Piyush Golari, 2years 7months, Male
Father's Name :DamruGolari
Address :Santinagar, BLOCK-koraput, DIST-Koraput
Diagnosis:Mild ASD
Treated by :Occupational Therapist, DEIC, RBSK, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

Child came to occupational therapy with complains (from his parents) of fearful to unknown place, person & height, don't interact with peer groups, don't understand what parents says and speech difficulty. Then I did the assessment using SIPT module and found that he had multi-sensory defensiveness, minimal maintenance of eye contact with poor attention span, poor fine motor & gross motor functions, low muscle tone with gravitational insecurity, ADLs difficulties and maladaptive behaviors.

Therapeutic Intervention:

After the findings I planned a weekly occupational therapy programme which includes; - sensory integration therapy, ball catching & throwing, swing activities, jumping and slinding, activities inside ball pool, animal walks, different puzzle activities with peg board, brain gym, imitation activities and group therapy.

Post-Intervention condition

After few months of therapy, the child shows a remarkable improvement in attention span and sitting tolerance, Vestibular & auditory, now follows all instructions, hand functions (grip & pinch strength) and due to group therapy peer group interaction also improved little bit.

The parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC, RBSK.

Success Story of Tukun Khillo

Name of the Child : Tukun Khillo, 9yrs/M
Father's Name : GunayaKhilllo
Address : BLOCK-Jeypore, DIST-Koraput
Diagnosis : Down's Syndrome
Treated by : Occupational Therapist, DEIC, RBSK, Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child came to occupational therapy with complains (from his parents) of poor attention span, difficulties in balance and co-ordination while walking and speech difficulty. After the assessment I found that he has low muscle tone, poor eye-hand coordination, weak oromotor and having gravitational insecurity with sensory issues and he is very lethargic.

Therapeutic Intervention:

After the findings, I planned a weekly occupational therapy sessions which includes; multisensory stimulations, heavy joint compression through weight bearing activities, jumping over trampoline, balance & coordination activities and ADLs training for self help skills.

Post-Intervention condition

After few months of therapy, the child shows remarkable improvements in balancing and coordination with reduced sensory issues and now able to jump forward and backward independently (gross motor improvement) and shows improvements in fine motor skills. Now he has also worn his pant without help of his parents (Improvements in ADLs).

The parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC, RBSK.

Success Story of Ariyan Dash

Name of the Child : ARIYAN DASH, AGE -02 YEARS, MCH
Father's Name : N.N DASH
Address : RATHASHRMA COLONY, BLOCK – KORAPUT, DIST-KORAPUT
Disease : MILD AUTISTIC, SPEECH DELAY
THERAPIST : BIGHNESWAR MALIK (EI-CUM SPECIAL EDUCATOR)

Pre-Intervention condition:

On dtd. 30.06.2018, the child brought with his parent. When he came to DEIC the complain of his parents are he is not responding commands and following instructions, not sit in one palce fo doing some activities, poor eye contact, speech delay and not mixing with other children.

DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY SUGGEST

- The test used: MDPS SCALE and according to the test result the child is fall under Mild Autistic with Speech Delay.
- The therapy suggested for Psychotherapy, Behaviour Modification Therapy for improving eye contact and communication skill, Special Education and speech Therapy.

THERAPY GIVEN BY EI-CUM-SE

- Parent Counselling given.
- Home based therapy skill given for eye contact and eye hand coordination skill improvement.
- Behaviour modification Therapy given for increasing eye contact and communicating skill.
- Suggest for giving reinforcement for improving motivation for increasing attention span in some playful activities.
- Suggest for engaged him in playing activity with other children.

Present condition of the child:

- After therapy the child's attention span and eye contact is increased.
- Now the child sitting span increased.
- She is playing with other children and responding commands.
- Speech also improved after taking speech therapy.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of child.

Success Story of Rishi Pattnaik

Name of the Child : RISHI PATTNAIK, AGE -02 YEARS, MCH
Father's Name : SURESH PATTNAIK
Address : PUJARIPUT, BLOCK – KORAPUT, DIST-KORAPUT
Disease : CEREBRAL PALSY WITH COGNITIVE DELAY
THERAPIST : BIGHNESWAR MALIK (EI-CUM- SPECIAL EDUCATOR)

Pre-Intervention condition:

On dtd. 03.09.2018, the child brought with his parent. When he came to DEIC the complain of his parents are he is not able to sit and stand, speech delay, drooling, poor muscle coordination, unable to hold object, poor neck and head holding.

DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY SUGGEST

- **The test used: MDPS SCALE** and the child is diagnosed as Cognitive Delay with Cerebral Palsy and speech Delay.
- **The therapy suggested for Psychotherapy, Special Education, Speech Therapy and Physiotherapy.**

THERAPY GIVEN BY EI-CUM -SE

- **Parent Counselling given.**
- **Home based therapy skill given.**
- **Therapy given for improving Fine motor and gross motor skill.**
- **Oro motor therapy given for drooling control.**
- **Sensory Integration Therapy given by using sensory integration toys and tools.**
- **Different stimulation skill.**

Present condition of the child:

- After therapy child try to sitting with support.
- Try to reach object by hand and try to clap.
- Social responding improved.
- Babbling appear and control drooling.
- Enjoying the playing and social communication.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of child.

Success Story of Bhubana Pujari

Name of the Child : BHUBANA PUJARI, AGE -06 Year, MCH
Father's Name : K PUJARI
Address : KHUNTIPALLA, BLOCK – BORIGUMA, DIST-KORAPUT
Disease : BEHAVIOUR AND COMMUNICATION PROBLEM
THERAPIST : BIGHNESWQAR MALIK(EI-CUM -SE)

Pre-Intervention condition:

On dtd. 09.11.2018, the child brought with his parent by MHT team. When he came to DEIC the compalin of his parents are he is not mixing and playing with other children, Less communication (verbal and noverbal) with others, Poor academic Performance.

DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY SUGGEST

- The test used: BASCI-MR PART-B and the child is diagnosed as Behaviour and communication problem with Academic Difficulty.
- The therapy suggested for Psychotherapy, Special Education.

THERAPY GIVEN BY EI-CUM SE

- Parent Counselling given.
- Home based therapy skill given.
- Therapy given for improving Communication (Verbal and Nonverbal).
- Behaviour Modification Therapy Given.
- Motivation skill given to mother for how to motivate the children for mixing with others and share his daily activities.
- Counsel for continuing Special Education.

Present condition of the child:

- After therapy now the child playing with others.
- His academic performance also increased.
- Go to school and participate in different activities.
- Share his day today activities to his parents.
- Help to his parents on little household activities.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of child.

Success Story of Dhaneswar Gouda

Name of the Child : DHANESWAR GOUDA, AGE -03 YEARS, MCH
Father's Name : TULASA GOUDA
Address : SUKULIGUDA, BLOCK – BORIGUMA, DIST-KORAPUT
Disease : CEREBRAL PALSY WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY
THERAPIST : BIGHNESWAR MALIK (EI –SPECIAL EDUCATOR)

Pre-Intervention condition:

On dtd. 16.09.2016, the child is identified by MHT Boriguma and brought with his parent to DEIC. When he came to DEIC the complain of his parents are she is unable to stand and walk, speech delay, poor muscle coordination, unable to hold object and not following instruction, not able to doing daily activities.

DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY SUGGEST

- The test used: **MDPS SCALE** and the child is diagnosed as **Mild Intellectual Disability with Cerebral Palsy, Speech Delay.**
- The therapy suggested for **Psychotherapy, Special Education, Speech Therapy and Physiotherapy.**

THERAPY GIVEN BY EI-CUM-SE

- **Parent Counselling given.**
- **Home based therapy skill given.**
- **Therapy given for improving Fine motor and gross motor skill.**
- **Object identification skill given.**
- **Sensory Integration Therapy given by using sensory integration toys and tools.**
- **Different stimulation skill.**

Present condition of the child:

- After therapy now the child is able to stand by self and walk with support.
- Now the child is try to speak some words.
- The child is trying reaching object and playing with objects.
- Doing some daily activities with help.
- Enjoying the play therapy.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of child.

Success Story of Elina Digal

Name of the Child : ELINA DIGAL, AGE -05 YEARS, FCH
Father's Name : BAPUJI DIGAL
Address : POLICE COLONY, BLOCK – KORAPUT, DIST-KORAPUT
Disease : CEREBRAL PALSY WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY
THERAPIST : BIGHNESWAR MALIKI (EI-CUM SPECIAL EDUCATOR)

Pre-Intervention condition:

On dtd. 10.11.2018, the child brought with her parent. When she came to DEIC the complain of her parents are she is not able to stand and walk, speech not clear, drooling, poor muscle coordination, unable to hold object, not able to doing daily activities.

DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY SUGGEST

- **The test used: MDPS SCALE and the child is diagnosed as Mild Intellectual Disability with Cerebral Palsy, Unclear Speech.**
- **The therapy suggested for Psychotherapy, Special Education, Speech Therapy and Physiotherapy.**

THERAPY GIVEN BY EI-CUM-SE

- **Parent Counselling given.**
- **Home based therapy skill given.**
- **Therapy given for improving Fine motor and gross motor skill.**
- **Oro motor therapy given for drooling control.**
- **Counting numbers and special education training given.**
- **Sensory Integration Therapy given by using sensory integration toys and tools.**
- **Different stimulation skill.**

Present condition of the child:

- **After therapy now the child is able to stand by self and walk with support.**
- **Now the child is try to speak some sentences.**
- **The child is holding some objects and through ball.**
- **Doing some daily activities with help.**
- **Enjoying the playing and social communication.**

Now she is coming to DEIC for continuing her therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of child.

Success Story of Hemanta Gouda

Name of the Child : HEMANTA GOUDA, AGE -05 YEARS, MCH
Father's Name : JAYANTA GOUDA
Address : PARLI, BLOCK – BORIGUMA, DIST-KORAPUT
Disease : MODERATE INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY WITH SPEECH DELAY
THERAPIST : BIGHNESWAR MALIK(EI CUM –SPECIAL EDUCATOR)

Pre-Intervention condition:

On dtd. 24.05.2019, the child is identified by MHT Boriguma and brought with his parent to DEIC. When he came to DEIC the complain of his parents are he is not respoding commands, speech delay, deficit in adapive behaviour and academic performance.

DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY SUGGEST

- The test used: MDPS Scale and according to the test result the child is fall under Moderate Intellectual Disability, Speech Delay.
- The therapy suggested for Psychotherapy, Special Education for improving self help skill and academic skill, Adaptive Behaviour skill training.

THERAPY GIVEN BY EI-CUM-SE

- Parent Counselling given.
- Home based therapy skill given for how to doing daily activities.
- Special Education training given for improving academic skill and adaptive skill.
- Suggest for engaged her in play full teaching activities and giving rewards for improving motivation skill.

Present condition of the child:

- Now the child able to doing some daily activities.
- Sit in one place and doing some academic activities.
- He is playing with other children with using playing object.
- He is responding and following some commands.

Now he is coming to DEIC for continuing his therapy and parents are happy for the improvement of **child.**

Success Stories - RBSK KORAPUT

Haribandhu Gouda, S/o- Lachhman Gouda, At/Po- Charagaon, PS-Jeypore, Dist-Koraput, during the age of two years old was identified Motor Delay & Language Delay with difficulty in sitting, standing & walking and referred to DEIC by RBSK MHT. Haribandhu was provided mat exercise, therapeutic ball exercise, balancing in sitting, standing, positioning, remedial exercise, quadriceps table exercise, peg board alongwith Speech Therapy at DEIC Koraput. The parents were also advised to do Home exercise program twice daily. After regular therapy at DEIC, now the child is able to walk, run & speak and now he is included in AWC and parents are happy with the intervention of DEIC.

Ayan Ghosh, S/o- Mommed Ghosh, At/Po- Bapuji Nagar (Jeypore), PS-Jeypore, Dist-Koraput, during the age of 12 years was identified with Optic Atrophy (RE). Surgery was conducted on 11.02.2022 at LV Prasad Eye Institute, Bhubaneswar supported by RBSK He is recovered now.

Success Story of Lorence Pangli

Name of the Child : Lorence Pangli, MCH-4 yr
Father's Name : Babuli Pangli
Address : Bariniput, BLOCK-Jeypore, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: SAI SATYA SAI HEART HOSPITAL , AHAMADABAD
Treating Doctor : Dr. Asish Sapre

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was diagnosed by MHT-I, RBSK CHC Rabanaguda and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for confirmation. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput suspected the case as CHD and further referred to SCB MCH Cuttack for confirmation. ECHO was conducted at SCB MCH Cuttack and diagnosed as Congenital Heart Disease with VSD.

Again the child was referred to Sri Sathya Sai Heart Hospital, Ahmedabad for treatment through RBSK Odisha.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was operated at Sri Sathya Sai Heart Hospital, Ahmedabad on dtd.10.07.2021 free of cost through RBSK Odisha and the surgery is successful. Now the child is as a normal child and mainstreamed in normal schooling process.

The parents are happy with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Laxman Khora

Name of the Child : Laxman Khora, MCH-5 yr
Father's Name : Bhima Khora
Address : Goilput, BLOCK-Nandapur, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Club Foot
Treated Institution: DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was diagnosed by MHT-I, RBSK CHC Nandapur and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment in MHT vehicle free of cost. Surgery was conducted at SLNMCH, KORAPUT by SV NIRTAR TEAM during a camp on 04.04.2019. Regular follow up of the child was conducted at CHC Nandapur during the DEIC Screening camps & regular physiotherapy conducted at DEIC, KORAPUT by Dr. Satyabrata Mohapatra, Physiotherapist, DEIC KORAPUT.

Post-Intervention condition :

Now after Surgery, he is a normal child. He can walk properly now. His parents are very much happy with the RBSK intervention. The parents are happy with the intervention of RBSK.

Photograph During Surgery

Photograph During Follow up at home

Present Photograph

Success Story of Laxman Bhumya

Name of the Child : Laxman Bhumya, MCH-5 yr
Father's Name : Hara Bhumya
Address : Bayaguda, BLOCK-Jeypore, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Motor Delay & Language Delay
Treated Institution: DEIC Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was diagnosed by MHT-I, RBSK CHC Jeypore on dtd.20.03.2019 and referred to DEIC Koraput for treatment/therapy in MHT vehicle. After diagnosis as Motor Delay and Speech Delay by the Therapists of DEIC, she was regularly attended DEIC for therapy activities. Dr. Satyabrata Mohapatra, Physiotherapist and Smt. Aradhana Behura, Audiologist & Speech Therapist were played a major role in therapy for the child. Also home based therapy was conducted by the parents.

Post-Intervention condition :

Now after repeated therapy activities, the child is a normal child and able to Walk and Speak properly. His parents are very much happy with the RBSK intervention.

Pre-Intervention

Post Intervention

Success Story of Babita Muduli

Name of the Child : Babita Muduli, Fch-5 yr10month
Father's Name : Gobordhan Muduli
Address : Bogeyepadar, Mathalput, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Mathalput MHT-2 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at Aradhya ECHO CARE,Jeypore,where she was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was advised for surgery.therefore she was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.4162 Dtd.12.10.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-12.10.2023 free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Binesh Tamarbhi

Name of the Child : Binesh Tamarbhi, Mch-2Yrs
Father's Name : Kamal Lochan Tamarbhi
Address : Kasandi,Block-Nandapur DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Nandapur MHT-1 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at Aradhya ECHO CARE,Jeypore,where He was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was advised for surgery.Therefore he was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.2150 Dtd.18.07.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-25.07.2023 ,free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Samuel Mandi

Name of the Child : Samuel Mandi, Mch-2Yrs
Father's Name : Shyam Mandi
Address : Nandaka,Block-Nandapur DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Mumbai SRCC
Treating Doctor : Dr.Supratim Sen

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Nandapur MHT-1 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test. The 2D ECHO test was conducted in a Camp held at SATYA SAI HEART HOSPITAL, BHUBANESWAR, where he was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was advised to do surgery. Therefore he was referred to SRCC MUMBAI, along with ESCORT Sujit kumar Nayak (PHARMACIST) and the travelling allowance was Beared by RBSK, vide letter No.2411 dtd.05.08.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at SRCC MUMBAI on dt.-14.08.2023 ,free of cost through RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of pritam Huika

Name of the Child : Pritam Huika, Mch-1.6 yr
Father's Name : Nari Huika
Address : Kutudi, BLOCK-Narayanpatna, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Narayanpatna MHT-1 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at ARADHYA ECHO CARE Jeypore, where he was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was adviced for surgery, therefore He was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.1932 dtd.03.07.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-10.04.2023 free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Lalita Hikoka

Name of the Child : Lalita Hikoka, Mch-12 yr
Name of Father : Wachu Hikoka
Address : Khajaguda, BLOCK-Narayanpatna, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Clubfoot (Both Leg)
Treated Institution:DHH , Jeypore
Treating Doctor : Dr.Deepak Singh & Dr.Promod Ku Parid

Pre-Intervention condition:

The patient LALITA HIKOKA was identified with clubfoot of both the legs by Narayanpatna MHT-1 while screening at AWC, she was counselled for consulting a doctor but the parents of the patient refused. Over the time period the patient grew up and at the age of 12 she faced difficulty in walking long distances as legs would pain while walking and felt guilty about her disability. Again the MHT counselled the parents & patient by going to their dwelling place itself, and tried to convince them about advantages they will get through RBSK and their child will be able to walk again like other children. The parents were convinced and brought to DHH JEYPORE in the camp held by NIRTAR. Where one leg was operated successfully, then she was provided with shoes at DDC, Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

At present, the patient is able to keep the operated leg straight and is able to walk a bit properly. The parents are happy and satisfied with the intervention of RBSK and are willing to do the surgery of the other leg too.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Arun Harijan

Name of the Child : Arun Harijan, Mch-3 yr
Name of Father : A Hariajn
Address : Majhiguda, BLOCK-Boipariguda, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Cystic Swelling Rt Side Of Neck

Treated Institution: MKCG & MCH ,Berhampur
Treating Doctor : Dr.

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was observed with a swelling in the right side of the neck by the parents and it was simultaneously growing large day by day, the parents were worried about it and informed the concerned MHT. The MHT accompanied the patient to SLNMCH, KORAPUT and he was diagnosed by Cystic Hygroma on right side of neck by the doctor. He was advised to do surgery for which parents of the patient were counselled they agreed to proceed for the surgery. Surgery, was successfully completed at MKCG & MCH and the cyst was removed.

Post-Intervention condition :

Now the patient is normal. The parents are pleased with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of prince priya kandhapan

Name of the Child : Prince Priya Kandhapan, Fch-2.5 yr
Father's Name : Dhanurjaya Kandhapan
Address : Chandalguda, BLOCK-Dasmantpur, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Dasmantpur and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at MKCG,MCH Berhampur,where she was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was asked for surgery.therefore she was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.920 dtd.29.03.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-10.04.2023 free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Jesika Senapati

Name of the Child :Jesika Senapati , Fch-1.9 yr
Father's Name : Sabir Senapati
Address : Ashok nagar, BLOCK-Mathalput, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Mathalput MHT-2 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at ARADHYA ECHO CARE Jeypore,where she was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was adviced for surgery.therefore She was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.1781 dtd.16.06.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-22.06.2023 free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of K Sriyanhi

Name of the Child :K Sriyansi , Fch-3 yr
Father's Name : K Santosh
Address : Kenduguda, BLOCK-Kotpad, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Kotpad MHT-2 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at ARADHYA ECHO CARE Jeypore,where she was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was advised for surgery.therefore She was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.1015 dtd.05.04.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-12.06.2023 free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Dibyanshi Harijan

Name of the Child :Dibyanshi Harijan , Fch-1.3 yr

Father's Name : Siba Harijan

Address : Bamunigaon, BLOCK-Rabanaguda, DIST-Koraput

Birth defect : Clubfoot

Treated Institution: SLN & MCH, Koraput

Treating Doctor : Dr.Sandeep Belgeda , Koraput

Pre-Intervention condition:

The patient was born at DHH, JEYPORE with birth defect i.e. clubfoot of both the legs. The patient was assisted to the hospital by the concerned MHT vehicle i.e. MHT-1, the parents consulted the doctor and the patient was advised for bandage. Bandaging was done for 12 times, then she was advised for tenotomy. Tenotomy was done at SLNMCH, KORAPUT and then shoes were provided to her.

Post-Intervention condition :

Post intervention: Now the patient can walk properly. The parents are happy with intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Mahesh Nagabans

Name of the Child : Mahesh Nagabansa , Mch-11 Month

Father's Name : Tangu Nagabansha

Address : Kumudasil, BLOCK-Narayanpatna, DIST-Koraput

Birth defect : Cleft Lip & Palate

Treated Institution: SBM ,Balikuda (Smile Train)

Treating Doctor : Dr.Bibhuti Bhusan Nayak

Pre-Intervention condition:

The patient Mahesh Nagabansa was identified with cleft lip and palate by Narayanpatna MHT-1, while screening of new born at delivery point. The parents of the patient were counselled by the MHT at that moment and the patient agreed for visiting SLNMCH, KORAPUT for early recovery of the patient. The patient visited SLNMCH, KORAPUT, the doctor advised for CBC and to refer the patient to SBM for surgery. The patient got registered in DEIC and was counselled for carrying out of surgery for two times i.e. firstly, surgery of the lip and the second surgery will be of the palate after the recovery of the lip surgery; but the patient denied for the surgery. After, frequent counselling by the MHT and Social Worker (Amit Patnaik) the parents agreed for surgery of their baby. Then the patient was referred to SBM for surgery vide letter no. on dt. and was successfully operated.

Post-Intervention condition :

The patient is stable now and his parents are very much pleased with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Success Story of Suhana Khosla

Name of the Child : Suhana Khosla, Fch-7Yrs
Father's Name : Sahual Khosla
Address : Kebidi,Rabanaguda, DIST-Koraput
Disease : Congenital Heart Disease
Treated Institution: Kalinga Hospital Bhubaneswar
Treating Doctor : Dr.Pankaj Kumar Mishra, BBSR

Pre-Intervention condition:

The child was identified by MHT-RBSK CHC Rabanaguda MHT-2 and referred to DEIC/SLN MCH Koraput for treatment. The Specialist of SLN MCH Koraput Suspected the Patient for having Congenital Heart Disease and suggested for 2D ECHO Test , which was held at Aradhya ECHO CARE,Jeypore,where she was confirmed with Congenital Heart disease and was advised for surgery.therefore she was referred to Kalinga Hospital, Bhubaneswar through RBSK programme Koraput vide letter No.1163 Dtd.19.04.2023 of CDM&PHO Koraput.

Post-Intervention condition :

The child was successfully operated at KALINGA HOSPITAL, BBSR on dt.-23.04.2023 free of cost through BSKY card, under RBSK PROGRAM. Now the patient is stable and is able to perform normal day to day activities.

The parents are happy & satisfied with the intervention of RBSK.

Pre Surgery Photograph

Post Surgery Photograph

Results

This chapter is dealing with the client satisfaction, analysis and discussion of study findings.

A detail study was conducted to know the effectiveness of DEIC-RBSK Programme implemented in Koraput district. It was conducted as Client Satisfaction on 4D services provided by DEIC-RBSK Koraput through Google Form in online mode in preset questionnaires. Accordingly till date 752 nos. of Responses have been received Clients- Parents/Guardians of the 4D children with their views in Google from their Mobiles in a preset questionnaires (Detail annexed in Excel sheet in Annexure-I).

Responses are collected in Email ID – bibhumund@gmail.com

Analysis of data was performed according to the objectives of the study in the following sections:

Section 1: Sex wise analysis of 4D child (Male/Female)

Section 2: Block wise analysis

Section 3: 4D wise analysis (Birth Defect, Deficiency, Disease, Delay etc.):

Section 4: Surgical Intervention/Medicinal Treatment/Therapy Services/Counseling Provided

Section 5 : Feedback on all Services provided by RBSK Section 5: Block wise analysis

Section 6: Out of Pocket Expenditure for the cost of Treatment

Client Satisfaction on 4D services provided by DEIC-RBSK Koraput :

The snapshot of Client Satisfaction in Google Form is as below: 752 nos. of responses-

a. Sex wise analysis is as below:

Male –51.2% and Female- 48.8%

b. Block wise analysis is as below (Out of 14 nos. of Blocks under Koraput district):

Client Satisfaction Format as on 20-11-23 (09:30 pm)		
Sl. No.	Name of the Block CHC	Total Entry
1	Semiliguda	100
2	Nandapur	88
3	Bandhugaon	75
4	Jeypore	71
5	Kundra	60
6	Koraput	59
7	Pottangi	56
8	Boriguma	52
9	Narayanpatna	46
10	Boipariguda	43
11	Dasmantpur	35
12	Lamtaput	27
13	Laxmipur	21
14	Kotpad	19
TOTAL		752

c. 4D wise analysis (Birth Defect, Deficiency, Disease, Delay etc.):

Birth Defect – 283 responses received which is 37.6%
Deficiency - 109 responses received which is 14.5%
Disease - 95 responses received which is 12.6%
Developmental Delay & Disabilities - 188 responses received which is 25%
Adolescent Health - 33 responses received which is 4.4%
Others - 44 responses received which is 5.9%

d. Surgical Intervention/Medicinal Treatment/Therapy Services/Counseling provided :

Surgical Intervention – 300 responses which is 39.9%
Medicinal Treatment – 204 responses which is 27.1%
Therapeutic Services – 160 responses which is 21.3%
Nutritional Rehabilitation Services – 86 responses which is 11.4%

e. Feedback on all Services provided by RBSK:

Highly satisfied (Full Score) is 90.2%

Satisfied (Moderate score) is 9.4%

f. Out of Pocket Expenditure for the cost of Treatment :

Nil for Transportation in number is 737 which is 98%

Nil of Treatment in number is 720 which is 95.7%

Not satisfied with Transportation & Treatment is 03 which is 0.4%.

Discussion

- Timely updation of RBSK Software made possible to track the present status of status.
- Achievement in Screening by MHTs-RBSK Koraput is in increasing manner starting from 62% in 2014-15 to 103% in 2022-23.
- Coverage of screening at institutions (AWC & Schools) has been increased.
- Identification of health condition under 4D increased due to proper screening as per RBSK protocol (from head to toe by MHTs)
- Identification of Birth Defect at Delivery Point is increased so that early intervention could possible which made survival to quality survival of the children.
- Timely & proper Management/Treatment of identified children under RBSK Koraput has been ensured.
- Identification & management of SAM children has been increased so that improvement of nutritiounal health conditions of them is possible.
- Hearing Impairment children are being benefited by providing Digital Hearing Aid by DEIC-RBSK free of cost and can be able to hear the world. Cochlear Implantations are being conducted to the Hearing Impaired children which is also a very good success of RBSK programme.
- Visible birth defects viz. Club Foot cases are being managed so that children are able to walk, run & do their day to day activities perfectly without having Out of Pocket Expenditure. Also they are being prevented from peer bullying due to social stigma.
- Cleft Lip & Cleft Palate cases have been successfully treated through RBSK so that children are able to speak clearly
- Vision Impairment Cases viz. Cong. Cataract Cases, Developmental Cataract, Retinopath of Prematurity (RoP) cases etc. are being managed smoothly so as to enable the children to see the beauty of nature.
- Management of Paed. Cardiac Ailment cases through RBSK possible free of cost which enables the children to live in the mainstreaming of life.
- Continuous Capacity Building of Health Service Providers are being provided by National Master Trainers/State Master Trainers which enhances the knowledge & skill of them.
- District level Convergence activities with the line departments are being made on regular intervals for proper monitoring and mentoring of the RBSK programme.

Conclusion :

RBSK Programme is always providing a pre-designed effective platform for quality screening of the 0-18 year children including early identification of 4D's through Mobile Health Teams-RBSK for which it is now easy to manage/treat them at primary/secondary/tertiary level institutions.

Gaps in providing infrastructure and strengthening the secondary services at district level including equipping the health systems so that identified 4D cases can be managed easily minimizing the newborn/child death i.e. reducing the IMR/U5MR.

Incentive system may be initiated to identify birth defects at Delivery Points/SNCUs by the Staff Nurses/Medical Officers, so that they will be motivated to thoroughly screen from head to toe on regular basis.

Capacity building of healthcare providers may be increased so as to earn a better output in 4D services. Follow up of children through web portal i.e. RBSK Web Application can be strengthened so that each 4D child can be tracked at any level.

Recommendation:

Capacity building of all DEIC Staff including Exposure visits to different States may be provided so that it will be a conducive environment for implementation of all activities under DEIC & RBSK. Also more infrastructures including Equipment/instrument for screening of Newborns/children may be provided to DEIC for strengthening. Management of Birth Defects at District level hospitals should be strengthened.

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